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Economic Feasibility and Climate Effectiveness of Lithium-ion Battery Recycling in Europe

Master Thesis

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ABSTRACT

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are central to Europe’s expanding electric vehicle (EV) market and renewable energy storage systems, yet questions persist about raw material supply security and the environmental footprint of battery production. This thesis evaluates four commercially practiced recycling routes—Conventional Hydrometallurgy, Combined Pyro-Hydrometallurgy (two variants), and Direct Recycling—to determine their economic viability and climate effectiveness from 2020 to 2035 under evolving EU regulations. At the micro level, the analysis reverse-engineers each pathway’s cost and resource demands using an aggregate techno-economic (TEA) and life-cycle (LCA) model. Results show that for nickel- and cobalt-rich chemistries (NMC, NCA), hydrometallurgy and direct recycling meet mandated recovery rates and achieve positive margins, whereas pyro-hydro processes often incur losses and yield lower greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions. For lower-value LFP batteries, all existing processes remain unprofitable, although direct recycling narrows losses and offers higher GHG savings than alternatives.

At the macro level, a scenario-based analysis of end-of-life (EoL) LIB stocks in the EU indicates a significant shortfall in LFP recycling capacity by 2035, potentially undermining new regulatory targets. Policy interventions—particularly targeted subsidies for LFP recycling or R&D support for direct recycling—could resolve this gap. Additionally, standardizing battery design and digital traceability via “battery passports” would enhance the scalability of direct recycling. Overall, the findings highlight a strong interplay between technology selection, policy mechanisms, and market dynamics, emphasizing direct recycling’s long-term promise for both profitability and emissions mitigation in Europe’s emerging circular battery economy.

ABBREVIATION

BEV:	Battery Electric Vehicle
CAM:	Cathode Active Material
Co:	Cobalt
Cu:	Copper
DR:	Direct Recycling
EoL:	End of Life
EU:	European Union
EV:	Electric Vehicle
GHG:	Greenhouse Gas
Hydro:	Hydrometallurgy
LCA:	Life Cycle Assessment
LFP:	Lithium Iron Phosphate
Li:	Lithium
LIB:	Lithium-Ion Battery
NCA:	Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminum Oxide
NMC:	Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide
NMC-811:	High-nickel NMC variant (0.8 Ni, 0.1 Mn, 0.1 Co)
NCX:	Collective term for high-nickel cathodes
Ni:	Nickel
PHEV:	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle
Pyro:	Pyrometallurgy
STEP:	Stated Policies scenario
TRL:	Technology Readiness Level

1. Introduction

Because electric vehicles (EVs) generally produce fewer greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions than internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs) [1], and because mitigating GHG aligns with long-term human welfare [2], the electrification of the transport sector is gaining rapid momentum worldwide [3]. In 2024, the global EV stock grew by over 400% compared to 2020—rising from 3 million to more than 15 million units [3], —spurred by ambitious climate targets and policy incentives [4][5]. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) power most modern EVs, primarily due to their high energy density and improving cost competitiveness[6]. In addition to mobility, LIBs also support stationary energy storage systems for renewable energy [7].

With the rapid expansion of EVs and renewable energy, the demand for LIBs is rising swiftly. However, concerns have emerged regarding the sustainable supply of battery materials. These issues encompass the social and environmental impacts of mining and refining [8], [9], supply risks due to the manufacture capability and high geopolitical tensions [10] [11], as well as the availability and distribution of raw materials reserves [12] [13].

Given these challenges, recycling manufacturing scraps and end-of-life (EoL) LIBs has attracted considerable attention, especially among countries lacking domestic reserves of vital battery metals, such as those in the European Union (EU). By recovering cobalt, nickel, lithium, and other elements, recycling can reduce dependence on imported minerals while enhancing both economic and environmental sustainability. For instance, the use of recycled materials may lower battery production costs and support the long-term viability of EV manufacturing [14], whereas avoiding improper disposal helps conserve finite resources and mitigates land pollution [15]. In recognition of these benefits, governments such as the EU have enacted new Battery Regulations that mandate stricter recycling targets [16].

Against this backdrop of policy directives and market demands, it becomes essential to evaluate the economic and environmental performance of various recycling technologies to inform effective policy design. This research focuses on the 27 EU member states plus Switzerland as a primary scope for analyzing end-of-life EV LIBs.

1.1 Background and motivation

The subsequent sections cover EV and LIB fundamentals, uneven critical material distribution, LIB value chain and recycling technologies as well as recycling policies (Sections 1.1.1–1.1.5).

1.1.1 EV basics

EVs are defined as automobiles powered fully or partially by electricity stored in onboard rechargeable batteries, represent a transformative shift from ICEVs. Unlike ICEVs, which rely on fossil fuels, EVs convert electrical energy into mechanical motion using electric motors, eliminating tailpipe emissions and reducing dependence on hydrocarbons. The global EV market has grown exponentially since 2010s, as shown in Fig. 1. It is driven by three interconnected factors: environmental regulations, policy support, and technological innovation.

Figure 1 Global EV market trends in different regions, adapted from IEA [3]

First, environment mandates have been a primary catalyst for EV adoption. Transportation accounts for approximately 25% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions, with road vehicles

contributing over 75% of this share [17][18][19]. In response, governments have enacted stringent emissions targets. For example, the European Union’s 2035 ban on new ICE vehicle sales [20]. Meanwhile, the environmental benefits of EVs also depend on the electricity generation mix and battery lifecycle management—a challenge underscored by the EU’s Circular Economy Action Plan [21].

Then, policy also has positive incentives to accelerate EVs deployment. National and regional schemes, such as purchase subsidies (e.g., EU’s Environmental Bonus subsidies [22]), tax exemptions (e.g., US’s Inflation Reduction Act [23]), and charging infrastructure investments (e.g., China’s Guiding Opinions on Charging Infrastructure [24]), have reduced barriers.

Lastly, the technological breakthrough, especially LIB, which is the dominant energy storage technology for EVs, has accelerated the EVs adoptions to meet customer needs. Next section will introduce more on LIBs and why it is very important for EV adoption.

1.1.2 LIBs basics

Figure 2 LIB structure and components, adopted from R. Sommerville et al [25]

LIBs are complex electrochemical systems composed of layered components that work synergistically to store and release energy. As illustrated in Figure 2, a single LIB cell is structured as a stacked or coiled assembly enclosed within a protective casing (typically aluminum or steel), which prevents environmental exposure and mechanical damage. Internally, the battery comprises

alternating layers of anode (graphite-coated copper foil), cathode (metal oxide-coated aluminum foil), and a porous separator soaked in electrolyte (lithium salt in organic solvent). During charging, lithium ions migrate from the cathode (e.g., lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide, NMC) through the electrolyte, traverse the separator, and embed into the graphite anode. Discharging reverses this flow, generating electric current to power the vehicle.

As mentioned in Section 1.1.1, the technology improvements of LIBs are crucial for customers to accept EVs. LIBs - now powering over 95% of global EV production - have undergone transformative improvements since 2010: energy densities surged from 200 Wh/kg to over 550 Wh/kg [26], enabling ranges exceeding 400 km per charge (which is mostly cared by customers), while pack costs plummeted by 89% to less than \$100/kWh [27].

LIBs performance and types are mainly determined by the cathode materials, including the properties mentioned above, see Table 1 for a detailed comparison:

Table 1 Comparison of lithium-ion battery cathode materials, data source: [28][29]

Structure	Layered			Olivine	Spinel
Composition	LiCoO_2	$\text{LiNi}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Al}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$	$\text{LiNi}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Mn}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$	LiFePO_4	LiMnO_4
Abbreviation	LCO	NCA	NCM	LFP	LMO
Energy Density (Wh/kg)	630	750	750	550	400
Battery Price (\$/kWh)	300	120	80	60	65
Heat Stability	Low	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Life (cycles)	500	1500	1500	2500	1000
Use Model	NA	Old version Tesla	Tesla Y, Volvo	Tesla 3, BYD	NA

The performance metrics outlined in Table 1—energy density, cycle life, and cost—are intrinsically tied to cathode chemistry. For instance, high-nickel NMC cathodes (e.g., NMC811) achieve superior energy density but require 30% cobalt, while cobalt-free LFP sacrifices energy for stability and cost efficiency.

1.1.3 Materials distribution

As mentioned above, batteries are classified and defined by their cathode chemistries. However, the global supply of critical battery minerals—lithium, cobalt, and nickel—is heavily concentrated in geopolitically vulnerable regions, exacerbating supply chain risks for Europe. Over 70% of cobalt originates from the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), where artisanal mining raises ethical and environmental concerns, while 60% of lithium reserves are clustered in Chile, Argentina, and Bolivia’s “Lithium Triangle” [30][31]. Europe, however, holds less than 5% of all battery mineral resources, forcing reliance on imports to meet surging EV demand, which might not be sustainable. Such geographic imbalance creates three risks: price volatility, supply disruptions and environmental costs. To mitigate these vulnerabilities, Europe is prioritizing battery recycling as a cornerstone of its circular economy strategy. Section 1.1.4 will introduce the LIB value chain and technical foundations of recycling.

Figure 3 Global distribution of battery mineral distribution (background shading indicates mineral abundance, while circle reflects the proportion of each mineral within each regions), data source: [31].

1.1.4 LIB recycling basics

Fig. 4 below has illustrated the value chain of LIBs from cradle to grave. The LIB life cycle begins with mining and refining of raw materials, which are then used in cathode production, battery cell manufacturing, and module assembly. After usage, LIBs can either be filled underground or be recycled.

The recycling process consists of three main approaches: pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, and direct recycling. Pyrometallurgy involves high temperature smelting to recover valuable metals, mainly cobalt, nickel, and copper, but results in the loss of lithium and aluminum. Hydrometallurgy utilizes chemical leaching to selectively extract metals in the form of metal salts, providing higher recovery efficiency but requiring extensive chemical processing. Direct recycling, still in its early stages, aims to preserve the battery's cathode material structure, allowing for its direct reintegration into new batteries, thereby minimizing energy consumption and material degradation. More details of each basic recycling path can be referred to figure A.1 in the Appendix A.

To regulate recycling, different countries or regions have published their policy about recycling, which will be summarized in the next section.

Figure 4 LIB value chain with three basic recycling routes

1.1.5 Policy overview

Table 2 summarizes the policy trends to battery recycling in different countries or regions. EU and China move ahead with multiple regulations, especially on recovery rates.

Table 2 Battery recycling policies

Division		The policy trends related to the batteries recycling
 US [32]	The obligatory recovery of waste batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion of the responsibility of batteries recovery producers • Over \$100 million investment from Department of Energy in battery recycling infrastructure since 2019 with the goal of increasing battery recovery and recycling rates from less than 5% to 90%.
 EU [16]	The obligatory recovery of waste batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imposing the duties on battery producers for overall battery recovery, processing, and recycling.
	The requirement of recovery rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By the end of 2027, nickel, cobalt, copper 90%, and lithium 50%. • By the end of 2031, nickel, cobalt, copper 95%, and lithium 80%.
	The history management of the batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executing the battery passport system, which contains information about battery production, processing, and recycling for each battery in electric vehicles. • Battery labeling starts from 2027 (including information on usage period, charging capacity, recycling content, etc.).
 Japan [33]	The obligatory recovery of waste batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To protect the environment and secure a stable battery supply network, obligate recycling of waste batteries, such as electric vehicle battery recovery.
 China [34]	The obligatory recovery of waste batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrate the 'Battery Recycling Production Responsibility System', which recovers and manages the batteries from electric vehicle manufacturers starting from 2018. • Build a joint waste battery recovery and resale system with battery manufacturers, used car dealers, and waste companies.
	The requirement of recovery rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By the end of 2025, nickel, cobalt, copper 98%, and lithium 85%.
	The history management of batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a 'battery history management platform' and reinforcement of management and supervision system to monitor the entire usage period of electric vehicle batteries (production, distribution, recovery, and recycling), starting from 2018.

1.2 Literature review and gap

Interest in lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling has surged in tandem with global efforts to electrify the transport sector and achieve more sustainable energy storage. According to a bibliometric study by Z. J. Baum, the number of publications dedicated to battery recycling reached 3,596 by 2021[28]. The annual volume growth in publication on this topic (~32%) far outpaces the 4% average increase observed across the broader scientific domain, confirming that battery recycling is an emerging field of intense research activity. Generally, literature spans three interrelated domains: (i) technological innovation in recycling methods, (ii) lifecycle carbon footprint assessments and environmental comparisons, and (iii) economic feasibility plus market analyses.

1.2.1 Existing research landscape

For the three research domains mentioned above, the technology-focused investigations continue to dominate literature, branching into different levels of innovation and scale. The first cluster of studies refined matured processes such as hydrometallurgy or pyrometallurgy, modifying specific operational steps to enhance performance. Typically, this involves improving recovery rates or minimizing energy or reagent consumption. For example, D. A. Ferreira [35], A. A. Nayl [36], G. Dorella [37], and L. Chen [38] each examined comparable leaching-based systems but varied acid concentrations or reagent combinations to optimize throughput, often reporting incremental gains in metal recovery. Their work is largely experiment-based, emphasizing lab setups that quantify how adjustments in process parameters affect yields.

The second group of publications explores process innovation, applying different physical or chemical fundamentals to battery recycling. O. Kwon and I. Sohn [39], for instance, investigated advanced pyrometallurgical flows for recovering valuable metals such as cobalt and nickel, while E. A. Dalini et al. [40] shifted attention to hydrometallurgical leaching methods and solvent extraction. H. Ji et al.[41], by contrast, studied direct recycling, a strategy that aims to restore degraded cathode materials without fully breaking them down into elemental forms. These studies come in two main forms: review articles that summarize and compare prior experimental or theoretical achievements, and original research featuring lab experiments, computer simulations, or empirical field data.

The third type is more industry related. Industry-affiliated experts have also joined these efforts, bridging academia and large-scale industrial practice. Authors from industry and/or academia such as L. Bruckner et al. [42], G. Van Hoof et al. (all from the industry) [43], V. Velazquez-Martinez et al. [44], etc. highlight how commercialized processes must account for real-world constraints like equipment investment, logistical complexity, and regulatory frameworks.

In recent years, environmental considerations have become increasingly critical. Many new or improved recycling technologies are accompanied by life cycle assessments (LCA) to demonstrate their reduced carbon footprint. Beyond single-technology LCAs, some researchers conduct comparative evaluations of different recycling routes, scrutinizing everything from step-level emissions (e.g., acid usage) to comprehensive cradle-to-grave footprints [42-46]. These comparisons may differ in scope—some focus on region-specific electricity grids or unique cathode chemistries—while others vary their life cycle inventory (LCI) databases or system boundaries. Collectively, they point to substantial variability in results, reinforcing the notion that standardized LCA practices are still evolving. According to F. Arshad, as of 2022, 35 studies dedicated to LCA in battery recycling had been published, reflecting how mainstream environmental analysis has become in this domain [45].

Alongside technological and environmental evaluations, economic feasibility and market analysis is another focal point. Investigations into the financial viability of recycling processes consider labor costs, capital expenditures (CapEx), feedstock variability, and so forth. D. Deshwal et al. [50], for example, performed an economic analysis tailored to India's local battery recycling conditions, whereas X. Wang [51] explored how scaling up infrastructure reduces per-unit costs through shared overhead and improved operational efficiency. D. Steward [52] tackled broader market uncertainties, highlighting that cobalt or nickel price fluctuations can rapidly erode profit margins. In Europe, H. Heimes [53] and R. Sojka [53] mapped out the LIB recycling sector, documenting dozens of companies and emergent facilities, showing a rise of LIB recycling market.

Over the past few years, interdisciplinary studies have also gained traction. Some combine technical optimization with environmental metrics and cost modeling, investigating trade-offs and potential synergies among recovery efficiency, greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions, and net profit.

Table 3 below highlights several prominent examples of such integrative work. This new wave underscores the complexity of battery recycling, where no single factor—be it acid concentration or theoretical yield—can alone determine success at scale. Instead, practical solutions require balancing technology choices, environmental benefits, and economic constraints within a context defined by rapidly changing cathode chemistries and policy mandates.

Table 3 Interdisciplinary research of LIB recycling [11][25][46][54-56]

Researcher	Time	Research Style	Research Target	Research Scope	Research Method	Process involved
Ciez, R. E., et al	2019	(Use) Model	Environment + Economics (GHG per kg LIB + Cost per kg Cathode)	Processes + Production + Chemistries	Process-based cost + Attributional LCA + Monte Carlo	Basic pyro, hydro and direct recycling
Lander, L., et al	2021	Use Model	Economics (Profit per LIB pack)	Processes + Regions + Chemistries	Process-based cost + Sensitivity Analysis	Basic pyro, hydro and direct recycling
Sommerville, L., et al	2021	Quali. Framework	Economics + Resources	Processes + Companies	Strategic material Weighting And Value Evaluation (SWAVE)	Simplified commercial processes
Woeste, R., et al	2024	Model + Experiments	Economics (TCO & NPV per ton BM)	Processes	Accounting + Thermodynamics + Market Prediction + Experiments	Basic pyro + Lab hydro
Ali, A.R., et al	2024	Model + Simulation	Environment + Policy (CF per kg LIB; EU)	Processes + Chemistries	Process simulation + LCA	A detailed commercial hydro process
Cheng, A.L., et al	2024	Use Model	Economics + Policy (Cost per kWh LIB; US)	Production + Chemistries + Regions	Process-based cost + Scenario Analysis	Production

1.2.2 Critical research gaps

Figure 5 Interdisciplinary research topics mapping

Figure 5 illustrates how existing interdisciplinary studies cluster around three core dimensions—technology, economics, and environment based on Table 3. Yet no single publication addresses all four components simultaneously at a commercially relevant scale. Notably, A. R. Ali et al. [46] is the only research to incorporate the EU’s 2023 Battery Regulation [16], but it only examines conventional hydrometallurgy with policy required recovery rate without either a comprehensive economic assessment of its focal technology nor a comparison between other technologies. Consequently, while the literature reveals extensive technical refinement and environmental comparisons, it rarely integrates economic viability or policy-driven market dynamics—especially for scaled-up, commercialized processes. Against this backdrop, the present thesis seeks to close these gaps by evaluating multiple established recycling technologies in tandem with their economic performance, environmental outcomes, and broader market implications under evolving EU regulations. The specific research questions arising from this synthesis are outlined in Section 1.3.

1.3 Research questions and contributions

1.3.1 Set of research questions

Based on the literature review and gap identified in Section 1.2, this thesis seeks answers to the following research questions:

Core research question:

- How do policy-driven market dynamics shape the economic viability and climate effectiveness of battery recycling ecosystems in Europe (2020-2035), considering technological heterogeneity and cathode chemistry evolution?

Sub research questions:

1. Micro-Level Technology Comparison:

- Which commercially practiced lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling technologies can meet the EU's mandated material recovery rates?
- How do they differ in terms of profitability, cost structure, and greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation potential?

2. Macro-Level Market Dynamics and Policy Implications:

- How will Europe's end-of-life (EoL) battery stock evolve from 2020–2035, and do current or planned recycling capacities suffice to handle the projected volume?
- What will be the overall margin and climate benefits of the recycling industry with different recycling pathways and how policy tools, such as subsidies can influence these?

1.3.2 Research contributions

This thesis will contribute to the evaluation of EU existing commercialized LIB recycling technologies in multiple dimensions to determine their compliance with the EU's new material recovery targets. Rather than focusing solely on laboratory experiments or theoretical yields, this study integrates cost and revenue structures to identify where each process might generate sustainable margins. Second, the analysis incorporates greenhouse gas (GHG) calculations,

highlighting how different technological routes can reduce carbon footprints under real-world conditions, including reagent consumption and energy mixes.

Beyond micro-level process insights, this research extends the discussion to macro-level market dynamics in EU with estimates of the EoL battery stock from 2020 to 2035. By mapping current and planned recycling capacities against projected feedstock volumes, the thesis reveals potential capacity shortfalls or surpluses and explores how policy measures—such as subsidies or mandated recovery rates—could reshape the overall industry profitability and total GHG abatement. In doing so, it underscores the strategic relevance of advanced recycling technologies for nickel-rich NMC and LFP chemistries, where existing processes often fall short on economic or environmental performance.

Ultimately, the findings offer evidence-based guidance for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers, aiming to align recycling practices with Europe’s sustainability objectives and evolving regulatory framework.

1.4 Thesis structure

The remainder of this thesis proceeds in four main chapters, each aligning with the objectives and research questions outlined above. Chapter 2 sets the stage by detailing the methodology employed in this work, including the scope of analysis, data sources, and modeling approaches. It explains how the study focuses on two pivotal aspects—micro-level technology assessment and macro-level market analysis—while acknowledging the omission of a full closed-loop evaluation due to time and data constraints. Chapter 3 then presents the core results in two segments. The first segment (Sections 3.1–3.3) evaluates the techno-economic performance and climate impacts of four representative LIB recycling pathways, comparing their suitability for different battery chemistries and benchmarking their alignment with EU recovery mandates. The second segment (Sections 3.4–3.6) shifts to market-scale projections for Europe, examining whether current or planned recycling capacities can meet rising end-of-life battery volumes from 2020 to 2035. These findings extend to policy considerations, showing how economic viability and greenhouse gas (GHG) abatement might be influenced by differing chemistry distributions, technology adoption scenarios, and targeted subsidies. Chapter 4 provides a broader discussion, tying these empirical results back to the challenges of technological lock-in, capital investment constraints, and next-generation batteries. It also explores policy pathways such as standardized battery design, digital battery passports, and supply-chain strategies to facilitate new technology deployment and foster a circular battery economy. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes the thesis by summarizing key insights, limitations of the present study, and avenues for future research, offering recommendations to both policymakers and industry stakeholders seeking to strengthen the sustainability and competitiveness of Europe’s LIB recycling ecosystem.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research design and scope

This study originally proposed a three-step approach encompassing: (i) technology comparison, (ii) a comprehensive closed-loop assessment, and (iii) a broader market analysis (see Figure 6). However, constraints in time and data availability led us to focus on the first and third steps. Specifically, the second step—encompassing upstream and downstream modules such as battery pack disassembly and cathode remanufacturing—will be pursued in future research.

Figure 6. Overall research design: step (i) technology comparison (red), step (ii) closed-loop analysis, and step (iii) dynamic market analysis

Micro-Level Comparison of Recycling Technologies

Drawing on a comprehensive literature review of academic, patent, and industry sources, we identified four recycling pathways employed at commercial or near-commercial scales in Europe. These routes—Conventional Hydrometallurgy, Combined Pyro-Hydrometallurgy 1, Combined Pyro-Hydrometallurgy 2, and Direct Recycling—vary in their approaches to metal recovery, chemical usage, capital requirements, and technology readiness level (TRL) to recover lithium (Li), nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), and other critical elements. The four distilled recycling pathways are:

- Conventional Hydrometallurgy: Mechanical pretreatment is followed by acid leaching and solvent extraction, recovering metals (e.g., NiSO_4 , CoSO_4) in salt form.
- Combined Pyro-Hydro Process 1: High-temperature smelting (above $1700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) proceeds without pretreatment of battery cells, with subsequent hydrometallurgical steps.

- Combined Pyro-Hydro Process 2: Incorporates mechanical or thermal pretreatment to preserve more components—such as anodes or shells—before smelting and refining.
- Direct Recycling: Carefully dismantles batteries to retrieve cathode active material. A relithiation step then “repairs” the cathode, bypassing metal-salt precursor stages.

This analysis is conducted using a structured techno-economic assessment (TEA) and life-cycle assessment (LCA) model, informed by literature empirical data and industrial interviews[47], [57]. We benchmark these pathways against three broad categories of performance: (1) technology indicators (e.g., metal recovery rates), (2) economics (e.g., recycling cost, net margin in \$/kg), and (3) environmental metrics (primarily greenhouse gas emissions per kg feedstock). Detailed definitions and calculations for these metrics appear in Section 2.3.3 Aggregate model computation.

Macro-Level Market and Policy Analysis

Beyond comparing individual technologies, this work also examines the broader European market. Motivated by the evolving EU Battery Regulation, we concentrate on the 27 EU member states plus Switzerland, excluding the UK due to distinct post-Brexit trade relationships. Our analysis spans 2020 to 2035, aligning with key policy milestones set for 2031. This timeframe allows us to capture the typical 8–12-year lifespan of EV batteries (e.g., Tesla, BYD [58][59]), and limiting speculative long-range forecasts. We evaluate how various policy scenarios shape recycling-market size, economic feasibility, and environmental performance within this window. Going beyond 2035 would introduce greater uncertainties in technology trajectories and regulatory developments, which we leave for subsequent studies.

By pairing micro-level insights on recycling processes with a macro-scale policy and market analysis, this research offers an integrative perspective on how technology choices, evolving regulations, and economic drivers could interact to shape lithium-ion battery recycling in Europe.

2.2 Data collection and sources

To capture the breadth of technical, economic, and policy considerations in lithium-ion battery recycling, this study draws on four main categories of data. Each category underpins a distinct

aspect of the analysis—ranging from process design to macro-level market trends—and all final parameters are fully documented in Appendix B.

1. **Technology Data:** We collected process flow diagrams, equipment specifications, and material throughput parameters for each recycling pathway from academic publications, engineering patents, commercial white papers, and semi-structured industry interviews. This multifaceted approach enabled us to reconstruct realistic process models, even when companies withheld proprietary details.
2. **Economic Data:** Capital and operating costs, labor wages, metal prices, and inflation factors were compiled from both open-access and private databases, including the RWTH battery company dataset [60], a master thesis from ETH [61], and the EverBatt model from Argonne National Laboratory [57]. To reflect local variations, regional differentials were applied, ensuring region-specific economic inputs, for example, table B.3 in the Appendix.
3. **Environmental Data:** We sourced life-cycle emission factors for greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) and regulated pollutants (e.g., NO_x, SO_x, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, etc.) from GREET 2022 [62] and Ecoinvent 3.8 [63]. These databases also provide region-specific electricity mixes, allowing us to capture variations in grid carbon intensity and energy profiles across Europe, see table B.4-6 in the Appendix.
4. **Market and Policy Data:** Projected end-of-life battery volumes, historical sector growth rates, and facility capacities were extracted from the IEA's Global EV Outlook 2024 [3], academic studies [64], and official EU documents [63][64]. This information informed scenario-building for policy interventions and capacity expansions, linking micro-level process results to broader market dynamics.

Where data proved unavailable or contradictory, we used expert judgment or secondary references to reconcile discrepancies. For instance, when multiple sources reported different cost estimates for specific equipment, we employed median values or cross-checked them against pilot-facility data.

2.3 Analytic steps, tools, and formulas

2.3.1 Overview of analytical workflow

As outlined in Section 2.1, this study operates at two levels: a micro-level technology comparison and a macro-level market analysis. Here, we describe the integrated steps that connect both dimensions for lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling. The methodology unfolds in two main phases. First, we evaluate specific recycling pathways at a nominal commercial scale—focusing on their techno-economic performance and environmental footprints—using the EverBatt model developed by Argonne National Laboratory[57]). Second, these per-kilogram results feed into various market scenarios [64], enabling estimations of how policy or market shifts could affect overall profitability and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within Europe’s recycling sector.

Figure 7 Analytical workflow for technology comparisons

Within this framework, Figure 7 above illustrates the first phase, i.e. how the TEA-LCA model quantifies both economic and environment impacts for different recycling routes. Because EverBatt model itself does not encompass every engineering or thermodynamic detail, we adopt a

“process reverse engineering” approach to establish realistic inputs—such as equipment use and reagent needs—for each pathway. After computing metrics like cost in \$/kg or GHG in kg CO₂-eq/kg feedstock, we employ “Scenarios of EoL Battery Stocks” to extrapolate these micro-level findings to a dynamic European context from 2020 to 2035.

2.3.2 Process reverse engineering

A major challenge in analyzing real-world recycling technologies stems from the limited transparency of industrial data, as most companies treat detailed process flow sheets and equipment specifications as trade secrets. Consequently, our first goal was to reconstruct each recycling pathway at sufficient resolution—identifying key equipment and operational parameters—to facilitate robust cost and emissions modeling in EverBatt, acknowledging that certain facility-specific details remain undisclosed.

To begin, we surveyed the literature and patent landscape, drawing upon academic journals, conference proceedings, corporate technical reports, and publicly accessible patent documents. While these sources typically outline core concepts (e.g., acid leaching, pyro-smelting, or direct relithiation), they seldom provide granular information on machinery selection or detailed design parameters such as reactor dimensions and energy consumption.

We then bridged these gaps through semi-structured interviews with battery recycling experts (see Appendix C), including academic researchers and engineers from pilot plants. Their qualitative insights—ranging from approximate reaction yields to cost adjustment factors—were combined with established chemical engineering references. In particular, we used stoichiometric relationships to infer reagent consumption (e.g., acid concentrations or fluxes for high-temperature processes; these data can be obtained from the hydrometallurgy handbook, authored by J. Jung et al. [67]) and standard equipment catalogs or empirical formulae to estimate typical throughput capacities and power demands [68].

The resulting “reverse-engineered” flowsheets capture each major unit operation—shredders, leaching reactors, kilns, supercritical CO₂ extractors—and its associated resource requirements. For instance, in “Conventional Hydrometallurgy,” we distinguish three stages: mechanical

pretreatment, acid leaching, and solvent extraction, each with specific equipment and reagent inputs. These conceptual yet numerically coherent flowsheets establish a solid baseline for subsequent EverBatt computations, ensuring that each recycling pathway is modeled with realistic engineering fidelity for both cost and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

As an example, Figure 8 shows the flowsheet for Conventional Hydrometallurgy (Pathway 1), highlighting the major steps (e.g., shredding, sorting, acid leaching, and solvent extraction) along with key reagents. Parallel flowsheets for the other routes (Pyro-Hydro 1, Pyro-Hydro 2, Direct Recycling) are presented in Appendix A.

Figure 8 Equipment flowsheet of conventional hydrometallurgy

2.3.3 Aggregate model computation

Having established the conceptual process flows, we integrate these inputs into EverBatt, a comprehensive techno-economic and life-cycle assessment model. Fundamentally, EverBatt represents each recycling pathway as a set of aggregated resource demands and outputs—including chemicals, utilities, labor hours, and capital equipment—and applies standardized cost functions and emission factors to derive key performance metrics.

For instance, the total recycling cost, expressed in \$/kg of feedstock, is computed by summing three primary components: (i) direct expenditures on equipment, reagents, labor, and utilities, (ii) indirect costs, including overhead and contingency, as prescribed by established chemical engineering cost estimation framework [68][69], and (iii) any applicable recycling fees or adjustments related to battery feed costs. Notably, in this study, we do not account for potential recycling fees or subsidies. Instead, if the net margin per kilogram of feedstock is negative, it implies that an external financial incentive—either a fee or subsidy—would be required to ensure the economic viability of battery recycling.

In addition to the cost functions mentioned above (see equations (1)~(8) in Appendix D), it is also necessary to mention that the individual equipment costs require scale adjustments when it moves away from a reference capacity due to the data availability. Typically, a vendor quote or catalog entry provides a baseline price, $Price_{Equip,i}(R_0)$, at some nominal throughput R_0 . However, in practice, actual facilities may operate at throughput R that is higher or lower. To account for such differences, we adopt the classical power-law scaling rule from chemical engineering design:

$$Price_{equip,i}(R) = \left[Price_{equip,i}(R_0) \times \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^p + k \right] \times Adjustment\ Factor_i$$

where p is an empirically derived exponent (commonly in the range 0.5–1.0), k is a constant offset, and *Adjustment Factor* accounts for regional or equipment-specific cost modifiers. The exponent p reflects economies of scale, recognizing that a doubling of throughput typically increases equipment cost by less than a factor of two. All specific parameter values (including the numerical ranges for p and k) are summarized in Appendix E.

It is important to note that the subscript i does not carry a uniform meaning across equations; for example, in the context of equipment-related costs, i denotes a specific piece of equipment, whereas in reagent cost calculations, it refers to an individual type of reagent.

A summary of the key cost components and computational methodology is provided in Table 3.1, which serves as a simplified example, while a detailed compilation of the factors used for estimation—particularly those governing indirect cost adjustments—is available in Appendix F.

Table 4 Example of cost items and estimation method

Cost Items	Computed/Estimated as
I. Direct Investment	$I.A + I.B + I.C + I.D$
A. Equipment	$I.A.1 + I.A.2 + I.A.3 + I.A.4 + I.A.5$
1. Purchased equipment	Sum of (equipment * unit cost)
2. Installation	40% of I.A.1
...	
II. Indirect Investment	$II.A + II.B + II.C$
A. Engineering and supervision	10% of I
B. Construction expense and contractor's fee	10% of I
C. Contingency	5% of I
III. Fixed Capital Investment	$I + II$
IV. Working Capital	10% of III
V. Total Capital Investment	$III + IV$
VI. Manufacturing Costs	$VI.A + VI.B + VI.C$
A. Direct product costs	$VI.A.1 + VI.A.2 + VI.A.3 + \dots$
1. Raw material / reagent	Sum of (reagent * unit cost)
2. Operating Labor	Sum of (labor * hours * salary)
4. Utility (energy / water)	Sum of (utility * unit cost)
...	
B. Fixed charges	$VI.B.1 + VI.B.2 + VI.B.3 + VI.B.4 + VI.B.5$
1. Depreciation	$(III - I.D) / \text{plant lifetime}$
...	
VII. General Expense	$VII.A + VII.B + VII.C$
...	
VIII. Total Product Cost	$VI + VII$

Revenue is derived by multiplying the mass of recovered materials (e.g., nickel or cobalt in salt) by respective market prices. Subtracting total costs from total revenues yields a net margin which can be positive, zero, or even negative depending on the chemistry and market conditions, see equations below.

$$\text{Recycling Cost} = \frac{\text{Total Direct Cost} + \text{Total Indirect Cost}}{\text{Facility Capacity}}$$

$$\text{Revenue} = \sum_i \text{Product}_i \times \text{Unit Price}_i$$

$$\text{Margin} = \text{Revenue} - \text{Recycling Cost}$$

On the environmental side, we applied life-cycle inventory (LCI) approach partitions greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions into three major sources. First, material footprints arise from producing or transporting any chemical reagents (e.g., sulfuric acid for hydrometallurgy) prior to use; these embodied emissions typically come from databases such as Ecoinvent or GREET, where each kilogram of reagent has a pre-assigned carbon intensity. Second, energy footprints stem from the electricity or fuel consumed to power the recycling equipment—be it a pyrometallurgical furnace operating at high temperature or mechanical shredders in a pretreatment step. We again rely on standard emission factors (e.g., kg CO₂-eq/kWh) to convert total energy demand into an environmental burden. Finally, process reaction emissions are estimated from stoichiometric relationships embedded. For instance, when an NMC811 cathode (LiNi_{0.8}Co_{0.1}Mn_{0.1}O₂) undergoes pyro-smelting, partial decomposition and carbothermic reduction yield Ni metal and CO₂, as illustrated by Reaction (1) and Reaction (2) [67]. Each kilogram of recycled NMC811 feedstock (10.28 mol) will have 0.19 kg CO₂ (4.4 mol) emissions for Ni reduction in the pyrometallurgy process. Summing up these three categories—materials, energy, and process emissions, gives the cradle-to-gate GHG footprint per kilogram of spent battery, see equation 3.12, where EF represents an emission factor derived from databases mentioned above.

As the final step in evaluating environmental benefits, we compare the cradle-to-gate GHG from recycling with the hypothetical emissions that would have arisen from virgin production of the same mass of recovered metals. Concretely, each recycled component—for instance, NiSO₄ obtained from the Ni fraction in NMC811—displaces an equivalent quantity of virgin NiSO₄, which would have originated from primary nickel mining, refining, and sulfate conversion. Thus, if a certain fraction of Ni is recovered at 93 % efficiency from 1 kg of NMC811, we multiply that recovered mass by the per-kilogram emission factor (EF_{Ni}^{virgin}) to estimate how much GHG we are “saving” by not mining and refining an equivalent amount of nickel ore. The same procedure applies to Co, Mn, Li, and any other recycled materials. Formally, let $mass_i^{rec}$ be the mass of component i recovered from 1 kg of spent cathode active material, and let EF_i^{virgin} be the virgin-production emission factor. Summing over all recovered components yields the total virgin-production footprint:

$$GHG_{recycling}^{total} = (\sum_i Material_i \times EF_i)_{materials} + (\sum_j Energy_j \times EF_j)_{energy} + (\sum_k \Delta CO_{2,k})_{process}$$

$$GHG_{virgin}^{total} = \sum_i (mass_i^{rec} \times EF_i^{virgin})$$

$$Net\ GHG_{saving} = GHG_{recycling}^{total} - GHG_{virgin}^{total}$$

The negative value of $GHG_{recycling}$ relative to GHG_{virgin} thus indicates an overall savings, i.e., recycling avoids significant emissions otherwise associated with producing virgin metals from raw ores.

2.3.4 Scenarios of End-of-Life (EoL) battery stocks

We first draw upon the global end-of-life (EoL) battery forecasts published by C. Xu et al.[64], which model future EV market development out to 2050 under two broad policy frameworks: a Stated Policies (STEP) scenario and a Sustainable Development (SD) scenario. In the STEP scenario, EV uptake tracks existing governmental commitments, whereas the SD scenario sets more ambitious goals, as shown in Figure 9. As C. Xu et al. point out, the SD scenario projects a significantly faster transition and much higher EV penetration worldwide, ultimately resulting in nearly double the annual battery demand compared with STEP. In our study, however, we seek a moderate or realistic outlook rather than the upper bound. Consequently, we select the STEP scenario as our baseline for global EoL battery flows, mirroring pragmatic EV deployment expectations to 2035.

Figure 9 Global EoL battery projection under two scenarios: STEP and SD, adopted from C. Xu et al. [64]

C. Xu's framework (see Figure 10) separates the analysis into two layers: an EV layer, which handles the total EV fleet and annual sales by vehicle type (BEV vs. PHEV) and by size class, and a battery layer, which allocates different chemistries (e.g., NCM, NCA, LFP, Li-S, Li-Air) to each

vehicle segment. Specifically, for each projected year in the STEP scenario, C. Xu et al. combine data on (i) typical battery capacities (66 kWh for mid-size BEVs, 12 kWh for small PHEVs, etc.), (ii) average battery lifespans and (iii) the evolving market shares of various cathode formulations. For instance, they outline one “NCX” scenario (where nickel-rich variants like NCM622, NCM811, and NCA rapidly grow) and another LFP scenario (where LiFePO₄ sees a larger share, especially in lower-range EVs). They also propose a “Li-S/Air” scenario, anticipating breakthroughs in lithium-metal batteries. Because the latter is highly speculative, we focus on NCX and LFP as our primary chemistry trajectories, consistent with mainstream industry deployments.

Figure 10 Framework of EoL battery stock estimation, adopted from C. Xu et al

C. Xu’s modeling framework merges two main analytic layers. First, an EV Layer tracks the evolution of both battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in hybrids (PHEVs), subdivided by size class (e.g., small, mid-size, large). This layer relies on external data—such as IEA or US DOE reports—for key variables like market shares, average motor power, and projected adoption curves. Second, a Battery Layer assigns specific cathode chemistries (e.g., NCM, NCA, LFP, Li-S, Li-Air) to each EV segment, reflecting technology trends and capacity requirements (e.g., 66 kWh for mid-size BEVs). Within this layer, average battery lifespans of 8–12 years are applied and adjusted to account for second-life applications and material constraints.

Within this two-tier framework, C. Xu incorporates multiple key assumptions to reflect real-world battery usage patterns (more assumptions are listed in Appendix G):

- Weibull-distributed EV lifespans ranging from 1 to 20 years (mode = 15).
- Declining battery replacement rates from 50% (pre-2020) to 0% (post-2020) as technology matures.
- Extended LFP lifespans of ~20 years versus ~15 years for high-nickel chemistries (collectively “NCX”).
- Second-life applications postponing recycling by 10 years for ~75% of batteries.

C. Xu’s forecasts are global, covering total EV stock and annual sales. To tailor these results to the European Union (EU) context, we combine multiple EU official estimates e.g., references [65][66][70] indicating that in 2024, Europe’s share of the global EV fleet stock is roughly 27.65 %, and its annual EV sales stand at about 23.13 % of the world total. We then average these two percentages to define an overall EU proportion (i.e., about 25 %), which we apply to the global EoL battery flows from C. Xu’s STEP scenario in each year from 2020 to 2035. Conceptually, if C. Xu et al. predict X million EV retirements worldwide in 2030, we assign $\approx 0.25X$ million EV retirements to the EU that same year, under the assumption that the region's relative market share remains consistent. In practice, the actual fraction could shift slightly, but this method captures a plausible middle path for Europe's portion of the global EV market.

Within the EU’s derived EoL battery stream, we then disaggregate the chemistries following the two main battery scenarios identified by C. Xu:

- **NCX scenario:** The market evolves primarily toward nickel-rich cathodes (NCM622/811, NCA), partially phasing out older NCM111.
- **LFP scenario:** LiFePO₄ gains more traction (assumed up to 60 % share in some medium-term window), while the remainder follows the NCX pattern.
- **Neutral scenario:** The average of NCX and LFP shares, representing mid-range battery composition trends.

Although more exotic chemistries (e.g., Li-S, Li-Air) appear in C. Xu's modeling, we exclude them for near-term analyses, given the limited industrial readiness. For completeness, we also define a "neutral" scenario by averaging the NCX and LFP shares year by year, producing a mid-range chemistry split for subsequent cost and emission calculations.

2.3.5 Bridging technology with market analysis

Having established both the micro-level technical assessments (Sections 2.3.2–2.3.3) and the macro-level EoL battery stock scenarios (Section 2.3.4), our final step merges these components into scenario-based market modeling. Conceptually, each year's projected feedstock of spent batteries (e.g., 2025, 2030, 2035) is allocated among four recycling pathways under two distinct frameworks: (1) current market distributions of recycling technologies, and (2) a new-technology deployment scenario, particularly focused on LFP. Below, we describe each framework in detail.

Current Facility Distribution Scenario

In this scenario, we compile data on established and planned recycling facilities (Section 3.2), classifying each by its principal pathway—Pathway 1 (conventional hydrometallurgy), Pathway 2 or 3 (pyro-hydro combinations), or Pathway 4 (direct recycling). Summing capacities across these facilities suggests approximate percentage splits among the four routes. For example, if the data indicate that 50% of available capacity corresponds to standard hydrometallurgy, 30% to pyro-hydro combinations, and 20% to direct recycling, we apply those proportions to the total EoL batteries arising each year.

1. **Linking with Chemistry:** Because the EoL feedstock includes multiple cathode types—depending on whether we assume NCX dominance, LFP dominance, or a neutral scenario—the fraction of each chemistry is assigned to each pathway in proportion to that facility's route share.
2. **Cost & Emission Aggregation:** For each year y , we compute the overall margin and greenhouse gas (GHG) impact by multiplying the micro-level margin(\$/kg) and emission intensities (kg CO₂-eq/kg) from Section 3.2 by the tonnage assigned to each pathway. The result is an annual weighted sum of per-kg values. Mathematically, if X_p is the proportion

of the total feedstock going to pathway p , and $Margin_p$ is that route’s micro-level margin, which is computed by equation 3.11, the aggregated industry margin for year y is:

$$Margin^{total}(y) = \sum_{p=1}^4 (X_p(y) \times Margin_p \times Feedstock(y))$$

A similar formula applies for GHG emissions:

$$Net\ GHG_{savings}^{total}(y) = \sum_{p=1}^4 (X_p(y) \times Net\ GHG_{savings,p} \times Feedstock(y))$$

New Technology Deployment Scenario

Alongside this baseline, we also envision a more radical shift to full adoption of direct recycling (Pathway 4) for LFP. According to interviews (Section 3.2) and specialized publications, direct recycling—still at TRL 4–5—holds particular promise for resolving LFP’s poor economic viability under conventional pyro-hydro or hydrometallurgical routes. Experts note that LFP recycling often yields minimal revenue due to lower-value metals, whereas direct recycling could restore cathode materials at reduced reagent cost.

Thus, under this scenario, 100% of LFP feedstock—once it enters the EoL stream—automatically goes to direct recycling (Pathway 4). Other chemistries (e.g., nickel-rich NMC) continue under the baseline distribution among Pathways 1–3. This approach significantly differs from the first, as LFP becomes the target for a new-technology rollout. We then compare two scenarios:

1. **Current Facility Distribution:** LFP remains handled by standard pyro-hydro or hydrometallurgy, often at a loss.
2. **Full direct recycling for LFP:** All LFP feedstock benefits from more cost-effective cathode repair, potentially increasing net margins.

Policy and Market Interpretations.

By quantifying differences in aggregated margin and GHG savings for LFP under these two scenarios—conventional pyro-hydro vs. direct recycling—policymakers and investors can gauge the economic and environmental value of adopting new technology. For instance, if the projected

gap in net margin by 2030 is around 1 million USD per year, any public support beneath that threshold would likely be cost-effective for advancing direct recycling. Conversely, subsidies exceeding that margin gap may not be justified on purely economic grounds.

Year-by-year scenario results therefore yield practical insights: if stricter LFP recovery mandates are enacted but hydrometallurgical routes yield negative margins, direct recycling (Pathway 4) may become critical to meeting regulatory targets without incurring losses. Likewise, volatility in raw-material prices (e.g., nickel, cobalt) could shift each pathway's revenue structure, underscoring the complex interplay between commodity markets and recycling economics. By integrating micro-level (reverse-engineered) process data with macro-scale scenario expansions, we gain a broader picture of how policy levers and technology deployment may shape the economics and carbon footprint of Europe's battery recycling over the coming decade. In Section 3.2.2, we compare outcomes under multiple feedstock volumes, chemistry splits, and regulatory contexts, highlighting diverse trajectories for profitability and GHG mitigation through 2035.

2.4 Method validation and limitations

2.4.1 Partial validation with real-world data

Because commercial recycling data is often proprietary, a comprehensive empirical validation of our model remains challenging. Nevertheless, we conducted partial cross-checks against three data sources: pilot-scale findings from patent literature and industry white papers, cost estimates from equipment vendors, and stoichiometric reaction yields reported in peer-reviewed studies. For instance, to verify our assumptions on energy demand during hydrometallurgical leaching, we compared sulfuric acid usage reported in a specialized handbook on battery recycling [67] and in an environmental report from a Chinese company (GEM [71]) to our model's default ranges; both sources fell within $\pm 15\%$ of our estimates. Likewise, for pyro-smelting in the Combined Pyro-Hydro Process, we aligned our scale factors (CapEx and OpEx) with public data from a European facility operating at approximately 7,000 t/year [72], yielding results of the same order of magnitude.

Although these spot validations cannot ensure perfect accuracy, they lend credibility to the broader cost and emissions calculations. A more rigorous approach would involve on-site discussions with project managers to gather proprietary information under nondisclosure. Finally, Section 3.1.3 presents a brief sensitivity analysis (e.g., on discount rate and Ni price) to show how robust or sensitive our outcomes are under key parameter shifts.

2.4.2 Alignment with established models

Our TEA-LCA framework integrates and extends Argonne’s EverBatt model, itself grounded in standard chemical engineering cost practices and the GREET life-cycle inventory. By employing recognized methods—for instance, the process cost model of Rocha-Uribe *et al.* [69] and emission factors from Ecoinvent—we ensure methodological consistency with widely accepted references in battery recycling research. While we customized certain parameters (e.g., European specific capital adjustment factors), the underlying structure remains aligned with the most used frameworks in the field.

2.4.3 Model scope and simplifications

- **Aggregate Process Representation:** Our approach treats each recycling route as an integrated “black box” of material inputs and outputs, rather than modeling every sub-step with detailed thermodynamics or kinetics. This simplification allows multi-scenario assessments but may overlook some trade-offs (e.g., variant reaction routes to save cost but have high emissions).
- **Generic Equipment Scales:** We rely on standard cost-scaling equations for chemical plants. Real-world capital expenses might deviate if a facility implements specialized, proprietary equipment, especially for different equipment in different regions.
- **Exclusion of Other Phases:** Because our scope extends from “grave” (EoL) to “gate” (reprocessed material), we do not consider the collection, transportation, re-manufacturing, etc. as shown in Figure 6.
- **Uncertainty in Future Market Prices:** Nickel, cobalt, and lithium prices fluctuate considerably. While we present scenario analyses for some price ranges, our model does not fully capture speculative market dynamics or unforeseen disruptions in raw material supply.

2.4.4 Data confidentiality and limited access

Many established recyclers treat their processes as trade secrets, preventing public disclosure of equipment specifics, operational yields, or cost break-downs. As a result, some of our input parameters—especially for advanced or emerging processes—stem from expert opinion or patent approximations rather than direct plant data. We compensated by using interview insights (Section 2.2) and cross-referencing multiple sources. Nevertheless, the model’s reliability hinges on these partial and sometimes non-uniform data inputs. In practice, collaboration with industry stakeholders would substantially improve accuracy.

2.4.5 Future improvements

Despite these limitations, the methodology establishes a workable TEA-LCA framework for multi-scenario comparisons. In the future, we plan to:

1. **Incorporate Additional Recycling Pathways:** e.g., for conventional hydrometallurgy, it can be divided into two sub directions: with or without thermal pretreatment. This will slightly increase the material recovery rate but more capital expenses.
2. **Refine Material Flow:** adopting a more detailed step-by-step model with stoichiometric or kinetic computation for certain steps, possibly using process simulators (e.g., Aspen Plus) for select sub-operations and check the trade-offs.
3. **Expand Geographic Scope:** comparing not only EU but also other regions.
4. **Add More Scenarios:** thinking about how material market prices influence the margin of recycling processes and supply increase due to recycling back influence the price of materials.
5. **Enhance Real-World Validation:** forging research-industry partnerships to gather actual yield/cost data from demonstration plants, enabling deeper model calibration.

Overall, while our approach rests on certain assumptions (e.g., scaling laws, partial stoichiometries, stable commodity prices), it integrates the close best available data in a structured methodology. The partial validations and alignment with recognized frameworks suggest that the results, while approximate, provide valuable directional and strategic insights into how recycling economics and emissions might evolve under diverse technology pathways and policy scenarios.

3. Result

3.1 Tecno-economic and environmental performance

3.1.1 Technology comparison

Key Points to Technology Pathways

In this section, four distinct battery recycling technologies are analyzed and reverse-engineered according to the methodology described in Section 2.3.2. Figure 4.1 offers simplified process flows for these technologies, highlighting each pathway's key steps. A more detailed flowsheet is provided in Appendix A.

Hydrometallurgy primarily involves two core processes: acid leaching and metal extraction (or precipitation). To improve the leaching rate—especially in terms of speed and efficiency—a pretreatment stage is essential. The most common approach is mechanical pretreatment, where spent (end-of-life) batteries are shredded or crushed to form a fine powder, often called “black mass.” This fine powder greatly increases the surface area available for leaching, thereby accelerating metal dissolution.

To optimize acid usage and enhance the purity of target metals in the solution (often termed the “pregnant leach solution”), recyclers typically implement a separation step before or after pretreatment. For instance, magnetic separation removes iron-based materials, while density separation discards lighter fractions such as plastics. While this step can boost metal purity, it carries a trade-off: some valuable metals may be inadvertently removed, reducing overall recovery. Nevertheless, without such a separation phase, achieving battery-grade purity in the final product becomes exceedingly difficult. This research adopts the most commonly cited separation methods from existing literature.

During leaching, various acids could theoretically be employed. In this study, however, a mixture of 98% sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) and 2% hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is used, as it has been shown to deliver the highest dissolution rate—a critical factor for maximizing metal recovery. Although extraction processes are generally more costly than precipitation-based approaches, they are prioritized here for their ability to achieve high-purity outputs.

Combined Processes 1 and 2 differ mainly in how they recover lithium (Li), which is especially challenging due to its chemical behavior during high-temperature treatments. In conventional pyrometallurgy—often exceeding 1700 °C—lithium tends to form stable compounds with aluminum or silicon, creating complex oxide slags that are difficult to process.

- Combined Process 1 recovers lithium during the pyrometallurgical phase by using replacement reactions. By introducing calcium chloride (CaCl₂) or magnesium chloride (MgCl₂), lithium forms lithium chloride (LiCl)—a gaseous species at high temperatures that can be condensed. This method requires precise temperature control and reaction conditions to ensure effective lithium capture.
- Combined Process 2 incorporates an additional pyrolysis pretreatment at moderate temperatures (500–700 °C) before the main pyrometallurgical step. Pyrolysis—a physical (non-reactive) decomposition—removes volatile components and aluminum from the feed, thus preventing lithium-aluminum slag formation and facilitating lithium extraction in subsequent leaching.

It is crucial to distinguish between pyrolysis (a physical decomposition at 500–700 °C that does not induce chemical reactions) and pyrometallurgy (a high-temperature chemical process above 1700 °C). Some publications mistakenly label combined processes using pyrolysis as pyrometallurgical, causing confusion about the underlying mechanisms.

Direct recycling, by contrast, focuses on recovering and restoring cathode active materials rather than breaking them down into elemental constituents. The central goal is to preserve the cathode's crystal structure to reduce both energy intensity and chemical consumption. After batteries are sorted by type and condition, a mechanical or pyrolysis pretreatment isolates degraded cathodes from other components. Subsequent steps vary according to cathode chemistry:

- NCM or NCA batteries: Because these layered structures tend to collapse as Li ions deplete, a high-temperature re-lithiation followed by structural repair is needed to restore usable cathode material—often called “new NCX powder.”

- For LFP Batteries: LFP's olivine structure remains stable despite Li depletion, so a simpler hydrothermal re-lithiation typically suffices, producing new LFP powder without extensive structural repair.

Currently, pilot facilities in China and Europe are actively developing and testing direct recycling technologies, particularly for LFP batteries, which are becoming increasingly popular due to their safety and longer life cycles.

Conventional Hydrometallurgy

Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy 1

Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy 2

Direct recycling

Figure 11: Simplified Process Flows of Four Battery Recycling Technologies: Conventional Hydrometallurgy, Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy 1, Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy 2, and Direct Recycling.:

Comparison of Recovery Rates

Figure 12 illustrates the recovery rates for four key metals, indicating that all examined technologies can meet the EU's 2027 target, although the stricter requirements set for 2031 remain difficult to attain.

The two combined pyro-hydrometallurgical processes exhibit broadly similar performance for cobalt, nickel, and copper—exceeding 90% recovery for cobalt and nickel, and nearing 91% for copper. However, their lithium recovery diverges: Combined Process 1 achieves 76.5%, whereas Combined Process 2 achieves 65.0%. The higher rate in Combined Process 1 likely stems from a targeted gas-phase lithium capture step following high-temperature smelting. These results imply that coupling pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical treatments can be highly effective for certain metals, even if lithium extraction continues to pose challenges.

By contrast, direct recycling demonstrates strong theoretical advantages, with reported lithium recovery of 88.0% and over 98.0% for other critical metals. Notably, these figures rely on a single literature source and differ from the stepwise recovery data used for the other pathways (as exemplified in Table 4.1 for conventional hydrometallurgy and in Appendix X). While direct recycling appears capable of meeting future regulations in principle, its practical effectiveness has yet to be confirmed by broader empirical data.

Based on these result and understanding of different technologies, Section 4.1 will discuss the technology choice, path dependency and transitions.

Recovery Targets in EU Battery Regulation 2023/1542				
	Li	Cu	Co	Ni
2027	50%	90%	90%	90%
2031	80%	95%	95%	95%

Figure 12 Comparison of metal recovery rates (Li, Cu, Co, Ni) across four battery recycling technologies, benchmarked against EU battery regulation 2023/1542 targets for 2027 and 2031.

Table 5 Recycling efficiencies across processing stages for conventional hydrometallurgy, including upstream, core process, and total recovery rates.

Conventional Hydro	Recycling efficiencies			Source	Annotation
	Upstream	Process	Total		
Disassembly Total		99%	99%	Assumption	
Mechanical Pretreatment					
Shredding	99%	100%	99%	Assumption	
Electrolyte recovery	99%	80%	79%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.173	Evaporation + condensation
Magnetic separation	99%	98%	97%	Assumption	
Zigzag 1, Aluminum		95%	95%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Zigzag 1, Plastic		90%	90%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	Including electronic components
Filter		85%	85%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	Sieving efficiency (for hydrometallurgy)
Air classifier, Copper foil		98%	98%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Air classifier, Aluminum foil		97%	97%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Air classifier, Plastic film		95%	95%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Hydrometallurgy					
Leaching	97%	98%	95%	Jung, J. (2023) p. 15-p. 28	H2SO4 + H2O2
Filter / washing		98%	98%	Jung, J. (2023) p. 15-p. 28	Graphite
Cementation / filtering		97%	97%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Cu
Precipitation / Filtering Fe		92%	92%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Fe
Precipitation / Filtering Al		92%	92%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Al
Co + Ni extraction	95%	99%	94%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	
Extraction Co	94%	99%	93%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	
Crystallization Co	93%	99%	92%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Co
Critallization Ni	94%	99%	93%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Ni
Extraction Mn	95%	99%	94%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	
Crystallization Mn	94%	99%	93%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Mn
Precipitation / Filtering Li	95%	80%	76%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Li

3.1.2 Margin and GHG emissions breakdown analysis

This section analyzes both the margin and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of four recycling technologies—Conventional Hydrometallurgy, Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy 1, Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy 2, and Direct Recycling—applied to two different battery chemistries: NMC-811 and LFP. This breakdown highlights the economic and environmental impacts associated with each process.

Margin Analysis of NMC-811 Recycling

Figure 13 Margin of NMC-811 recycling across four technologies

As illustrated in Figure 13 above, the profitability analysis of NMC-811 recycling reveals notable disparities among the technologies. Conventional Hydrometallurgy stands out as the most profitable process in three widely used technologies (without direct recycling as in the early stage), achieving a positive margin of \$1.44/kg feedstock with total revenues reaching \$5.43/kg feedstock. This success is driven primarily by the high market value of cobalt and nickel recovered from NMC cathodes, coupled with relatively lower capital investment requirements compared to pyrometallurgical operations.

In contrast, both Combined Process 1 and Combined Process 2 operate at a loss, with net losses of approximately \$0.02/kg and \$1.74/kg feedstock, respectively. The primary driver of these negative margins appears to be the high capital expenditures (CapEx) associated with pyrometallurgical equipment, such as smelters and furnaces. These processes demand significant upfront investment for a set of high-temperature equipment, which diminishes their economic competitiveness — especially in contexts where energy costs and operational complexity are high.

Direct Recycling emerges as the most profitable pathway for NMC-811 recycling, with a substantial net profit of \$4.87/kg feedstock. However, this result may not fully reflect its true economic feasibility. The apparent profitability is partly due to the fact that direct recycling directly yields cathode active materials (CAMs), capturing additional remanufacturing value compared to other methods, which recover battery-grade metal salts requiring further processing.

Moreover, some potential costs—such as sorting and material characterization—are not fully accounted for. These steps are critical for ensuring material uniformity, as variations in cathode chemistry (e.g., between NCM-811 and NCM-333) or differing states of health can complicate the relithiation process. These overlooked factors could significantly reduce the actual economic viability of direct recycling in practice. More details of direct recycling will be discussed in Section 5. Discussion

GHG Emissions of NMC-811 Recycling

Figure 14 GHG Emissions of NMC-811 recycling across four technologies

The GHG emissions data presented in Figure 14 highlight the environmental advantages of certain technologies despite economic challenges. Direct Recycling delivers the most significant environmental benefit, achieving a net GHG saving of 15.4 kg CO₂-equivalent per kg feedstock. This efficiency stems from the preservation of the cathode’s original structure, reducing the need for energy-intensive chemical or thermal treatment processes.

Conventional Hydrometallurgy follows with a substantial net reduction of 13.8 kg CO₂-eq/kg, primarily due to high recovery rates of cobalt and nickel, which offset the environmental impact of chemical usage and downstream processing.

The combined processes, however, exhibit lower emissions reductions, with Combined Process 1 and Combined Process 2 achieving net savings of only 5.8 kg CO₂-eq/kg and 7.9 kg CO₂-eq/kg, respectively. Beyond their high energy consumption, a significant contributor to these emissions is the use of coke for carbon thermal reduction during pyrometallurgical treatment, as reflected in Reaction 2. Additionally, while burning but not recycling graphite anodes can reduce the usage of coke, this introduces a trade-off concerning the abatement cost of recycling graphite, which could affect the overall environmental effect of the process.

Margin Analysis of LFP Recycling

Figure 15 Margins of LFP recycling across four technologies

The economic results for LFP recycling, as illustrated in Figure 15, show that all four recycling technologies currently operate at a financial loss. Among these, Direct Recycling incurs the smallest loss, at \$0.45/kg feedstock, making it the most economically promising pathway in the current landscape. This relatively lower loss is primarily attributed to simpler processing

requirements and the ability to directly recover CAMs, capturing additional value compared to other recycling methods.

In contrast, Conventional Hydrometallurgy, Combined Process 1, and Combined Process 2 all experience significantly higher losses of \$1.66/kg, \$2.81/kg, and \$4.15/kg feedstock, respectively. Notably, in all three cases, the net losses are greater than their associated CapEx costs. This suggests that simply scaling up production to dilute capital expenditures—an approach that could be viable for NMC recycling—is unlikely to turn these processes profitable for LFP batteries. The primary issue lies in the low intrinsic value of LFP materials, meaning that even with higher processing volumes, revenue gains would likely remain insufficient to cover costs.

Despite the current loss, Direct Recycling stands out as the most promising route for achieving future profitability. This method bypasses the high energy and capital costs linked to pyrometallurgical equipment and directly produces usable cathode materials, eliminating the need for further conversion from battery-grade metal salts.

This economic potential is already being recognized in industrial practice. Europe's first direct recycling facility was established specifically for LFP batteries, reflecting both the technical feasibility and commercial promise of this recycling pathway. Although the current LFP stock in Europe remains relatively limited, future growth in recycling capacity and advancements in technology are expected to drive down operational costs, making profitability more achievable over time.

Additionally, from a technical perspective, LFP batteries offer a significant advantage over NMC chemistries in direct recycling due to their stable olivine structure and simpler relithiation requirements. This makes direct recycling not only more feasible for LFP but also offers greater commercial potential in the long term. As technological improvements continue and economies of scale are realized, direct recycling could become the only pathway capable of achieving autonomous profitability for LFP battery recycling.

GHG Emissions of LFP Recycling

The GHG emissions profile for LFP recycling, illustrated in Figure 16, reveals notable environmental advantages for Direct Recycling, which achieves the highest net GHG reduction of 9.0 kg CO₂-eq/kg feedstock. This benefit primarily stems from LFP's stable olivine structure, enabling direct re-lithiation without the need for energy-intensive restructuring. Conventional Hydrometallurgy follows with a moderate reduction of 6.1 kg CO₂-eq/kg, driven by efficient leaching processes and relatively low energy requirements. In contrast, both Combined Processes demonstrate poor environmental performance, with Combined Process 1 leading to a net increase of 0.7 kg CO₂-eq/kg, and Combined Process 2 achieving only a minimal reduction of 0.2 kg CO₂-eq/kg, which has the same problem as NCM recycling.

Figure 16 GHG emissions of LFP recycling across four technologies

Overall Insights

The analysis highlights a clear trade-off between economic viability and environmental impact, influenced by both battery chemistry and process design. Direct Recycling offers the highest environmental benefits but faces economic limitations for NMC-811 due to technical immaturity. The structural collapse of NMC cathodes during use makes structure repair more challenging than for LFP, where the stable olivine structure allows for easier re-lithiation. However, for LFP batteries, direct recycling shows the greatest potential for future profitability, with the smallest financial loss and room for cost reductions through technological advancements and capacity scaling. Conventional Hydrometallurgy provides a balanced approach for both chemistries,

combining moderate profitability with significant GHG reductions, particularly for NMC due to the recovery of high-value metals like nickel and cobalt.

In contrast, the Combined Pyro- and Hydrometallurgy processes suffer from both financial and environmental drawbacks. Losses are driven not only by high CapEx from pyrometallurgical infrastructure but also by significant process emissions from coke-fueled carbon thermal reduction and the consumption of graphite anodes, limiting material recovery potential. Moreover, for LFP recycling, even increasing capacity is unlikely to offset these losses due to the low market value of recovered materials.

3.1.3 Sensitivity analysis

This section evaluates how changes in key parameters affect the profitability and environmental performance of battery recycling processes. The sensitivity analysis considers both material-related parameters (Figure 17) and non-material-related parameters (Figure 18), with variations of $\pm 10\%$ applied to each factor, i.e. the original parameter $\times 0.9$ or 1.1 . The analysis identifies which variables have the most significant impact on margin and GHG emissions, offering insights into where future improvements could be most effectively targeted.

Material-Related Parameters

Figure 17 Sensitivity analysis of material related parameters

As shown in Figure 17, the most influential material-related factors affecting profitability are the recovery rates and market prices of key metals, particularly nickel (Ni), lithium (Li), and cobalt (Co).

The analysis indicates that nickel recovery rate and nickel product price exert the strongest influence, with a $\pm 10\%$ change in either parameter resulting in a $\pm 16.5\%$ impact on profitability. This significant sensitivity reflects nickel's high market value and its substantial contribution to the overall economic return of recycling processes, particularly in the treatment of NMC-811 batteries, which contain a high nickel content. Improving nickel recovery efficiency or capitalizing on favorable market prices could, therefore, be crucial for enhancing profitability.

Lithium and cobalt also display considerable influence, though to a lesser extent than nickel. A $\pm 10\%$ change in either lithium recovery rate, lithium product price, cobalt recovery rate, or cobalt product price leads to a $\pm 6.4\%$ change in profitability. These results highlight the economic importance of maximizing the recovery rates of all valuable metals present in the battery feedstock, particularly as fluctuations in global market prices for these materials can significantly affect overall financial outcomes.

In terms of GHG emissions, only a few material-related factors show notable sensitivity. Among them, sodium hydroxide use has the highest impact, where a 10% reduction leads to a 6.3% decrease in GHG emissions. This result underscores the environmental burden associated with chemical usage in recycling processes, particularly in hydrometallurgical methods, where large volumes of chemicals are used for leaching and pH adjustment.

Other factors, such as sodium hydroxide price, soda ash use, hydrogen peroxide use, and the price and usage of sulfuric acid, show relatively minor effects on both profitability and GHG emissions, each contributing less than $\pm 1.6\%$ to the overall impact. This suggests that while operational efficiency in chemical usage remains relevant, material recovery rates and market prices of key metals remain the primary economic drivers.

Non-Material-Related Parameters

Figure 18 Sensitivity analysis of non-material related parameters

The sensitivity analysis for non-material-related parameters, presented in Figure 18, highlights several critical factors that significantly affect profitability, particularly those related to capital costs and production scale.

The most influential non-material factor is feedstock throughput, where a $\pm 10\%$ change leads to a $\pm 15.4\%$ change in profitability. This strong sensitivity indicates that increasing processing capacity can significantly improve economic performance by spreading fixed costs over a larger volume of processed material. Conversely, reductions in throughput can sharply increase the cost per unit of feedstock, negatively impacting profitability.

Capital cost adjustments — particularly in relation to pyrometallurgical equipment—are also highly impactful, with a $\pm 10\%$ change resulting in a $\pm 13.3\%$ impact on profitability. This finding

reinforces earlier conclusions regarding the economic burden of high CapEx for pyrometallurgical processes, where substantial investments in smelters and furnaces can limit financial viability.

The Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI) annual index further highlights the sensitivity of profitability to changes in capital costs, with a $\pm 10\%$ variation contributing to an $\pm 11.2\%$ impact. This metric reflects fluctuations in construction and equipment costs, emphasizing the importance of capital efficiency and careful investment planning in large-scale recycling facilities.

Financial parameters, such as the interest rate, also show notable sensitivity, with a $\pm 10\%$ change resulting in approximately a $\pm 6.4\%$ impact on profitability. This reflects the significance of financial structures and borrowing costs in determining the overall economic feasibility of recycling operations.

Other operational parameters, such as labor costs, facility lifetime, and annual working hours, have a more moderate impact, each contributing less than $\pm 5.3\%$ to profitability changes. Energy-related factors, including electricity and natural gas usage, show minimal influence on both profitability and GHG emissions, with less than $\pm 0.5\%$ impact recorded across all energy-related parameters.

Key Insights from Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis reveals that, for NMC-811 recycling via conventional hydrometallurgy, profitability is primarily driven by the market prices of recovered metals—particularly nickel—rather than improvements in recovery rates, which face practical and economic limitations. On the operational side, increasing feedstock throughput emerges as the most viable strategy for improving economic outcomes by diluting CapEx across higher production volumes.

From an environmental perspective, while optimizing chemical usage (especially sodium hydroxide) can provide incremental GHG reductions, the overall impact remains limited compared to emissions generated by pyrometallurgical pathways. Given these constraints, significant improvements in environmental performance will likely require a targeted selection of recycling pathways that are better suited to specific battery chemistries and material compositions.

In conclusion, future optimization efforts should focus on three key strategies:

1. Targeted selection of recycling pathways based on battery chemistry to maximize material recovery and minimize emissions.
2. Scaling up production capacity to dilute CapEx and enhance economic viability, particularly for high-value NMC batteries.
3. Refining chemical usage to improve environmental outcomes, although the potential for significant reductions remains limited in current process designs.

3.2 Market-scale projections

3.2.1 EoL battery stock scenarios (2020-2035)

As outlined in Section 2.3.4 (Methodology), the projections for Europe’s end-of-life (EoL) battery stock from 2020 to 2035 are based on the Stated Policies (STEP) scenario from C. Xu et al. This scenario provides a realistic forecast grounded in current governmental commitments and market trends, offering a more practical benchmark than the more ambitious Sustainable Development (SD) scenario.

To adjust these global projections for the European Union (EU) context, the global EoL battery stock is scaled based on Europe’s share of the global EV market—approximately 25%—calculated from the region’s EV fleet size and annual sales. The analysis focuses on two primary cathode chemistries:

- NCX: A collective category for high-nickel battery types, including NCM (111, 532, 811, etc.) and NCA chemistries, which are prevalent in high-performance EV markets.
- LFP: Lithium iron phosphate batteries, valued for their stability and cost-effectiveness, though traditionally less dominant in long-range EV applications.

Figure 19 below illustrates the projected EoL battery stock growth across three chemistry distribution scenarios within the STEP framework, alongside existing and planned recycling capacities in Europe:

- NCX Scenario: Projects the continued dominance of nickel-rich chemistries, leading to higher EoL stock for NCX batteries.
- LFP Scenario: Reflects an increased adoption of LFP batteries, driven by their growing popularity in cost-effective EV models and stationary energy storage applications.
- Neutral Scenario: A balanced trajectory that averages NCX and LFP market shares over time, capturing a moderate evolution of battery chemistry trends.

Figure 19 EoL battery stocks and recycling capacity under NCX, LFP, and neutral scenarios (2020–2035)

In the figure, solid lines represent the projected EoL stock for NCX and LFP chemistries under the three scenarios. These projections show exponential growth due to the rapid expansion of the EV market in Europe, with NCX stock expected to surpass 400,000 tons/year by 2035. Despite the rising market share of LFP batteries, their EoL stock is anticipated to remain significantly lower across all scenarios.

The dashed lines in Figure 4.9 illustrate the cumulative recycling capacity for NCX and LFP chemistries, based on a compiled database that incorporates research from Reyan and Archen, further refined through a certainty test. This comparison reveals a stark mismatch between projected EoL battery stock and the available recycling infrastructure, particularly for LFP batteries.

Estimating chemistry-specific recycling capacities poses considerable challenges, particularly when facilities claim to process both NCX and LFP batteries without specifying capacity splits. To address this uncertainty—and given prior findings that LFP recycling is often unprofitable—we adopt a 50–50 allocation for ambiguous cases. Without this balanced assumption, the dedicated LFP recycling capacity could drop to just 4 000 t year⁻¹, underscoring a broader underinvestment in LFP recycling infrastructure.

Even under the 50–50 assumption, two disparities become clear:

- **NCX Recycling Overcapacity:** By 2035, projected NCX recycling capacity surpasses demand, driven largely by higher-value metals such as nickel and cobalt.
- **LFP Recycling Shortfall:** Across all scenarios, LFP recycling capacity remains critically low. Despite LFP’s growing market share in EV and energy storage applications, its lower economic value discourages the investments needed to close this capacity gap.

These findings reveal a growing structural imbalance in Europe’s battery recycling infrastructure. While NCX recycling facilities are at risk of overcapacity, LFP recycling faces a potential bottleneck due to inadequate infrastructure. This issue has already sparked discussions within the industry, with some companies urging the EU Commission to consider exemptions for LFP batteries from stringent recycling targets, citing limited economic feasibility.

Addressing these challenges will require both targeted policy interventions and strategic investments to expand LFP recycling capacity. As LFP batteries gain prominence — particularly in cost-sensitive EV markets and stationary storage—ensuring adequate infrastructure for their recycling will be essential to fostering a sustainable and circular battery economy within Europe.

3.2.2 Economic viability under policy scenarios

Building on the projections outlined in Section 4.2.1, this analysis integrates micro-level technical and economic assessments with macro-level EoL battery stock forecasts, following the methodology outlined in Section 3.3.5. By merging these two analytical layers, we model how different market conditions and technological pathways influence the profitability of battery recycling in Europe from 2020 to 2035. Two distinct frameworks are considered:

1. **Current Facility Distribution Scenario:** Reflects the current recycling infrastructure, distributing EoL battery feedstock across existing recycling technologies based on market data compiled from operational and planned facilities.
2. **New Technology Deployment Scenario:** Envisions the full-scale adoption of **direct recycling** for LFP chemistries, which has the potential to address the economic limitations associated with conventional hydrometallurgical and pyro-hydro recycling routes for LFP.

Market Margin Under Neutral Scenario

Figure 20 Market margin of neutral scenario (2020-2035)

Figure 20 illustrates the annual profit trajectories for NCX and LFP chemistries under the neutral scenario (which was already described in Figure 4.9), where market shares between NCX and LFP are balanced over time, and existing recycling technologies are distributed according to their current market share.

The results indicate a clear divergence in profitability between the two chemistries. NCX recycling is becoming increasingly profitable, primarily due to the higher recovery rates and market values of nickel and cobalt. By 2035, the annual profit from NCX recycling is projected to exceed \$450 million/year. Conversely, LFP recycling remains consistently unprofitable throughout the projection period, with losses deepening as the EoL stock increases. This financial deficit stems from the low economic value of LFP's recovered materials and the lack of high-value metals, leading to a projected annual loss approaching -\$400 million/year by 2035. When combining both chemistries, the overall market remains profitable due to NCX's strong financial performance. However, the cumulative losses from LFP recycling significantly erode the total margin, highlighting a structural imbalance within the recycling sector.

These findings underscore the economic risks associated with scaling LFP recycling using conventional technologies, given its consistently negative margins.

Market Margin Across Chemistry Scenarios

Figure 21 Market margin across three chemistry scenarios (2020-2035)

Figure 21 extends this analysis by applying the same market-based technology distribution under three distinct chemistry scenarios: NCX, LFP and Neutral Scenarios as described in Figure 19.

Under the NCX-Dominant Scenario, the market remains highly profitable, driven by the strong economic return from recovering high-value metals. By 2035, profits could surpass \$500 million/year. In the Neutral Scenario, profits are more modest but still positive, as gains from NCX recycling continue to offset LFP losses. The LFP-Dominant Scenario paints a starkly different picture, with the entire market becoming unprofitable by the early 2030s. Annual losses deepen as LFP's share of the EoL stock grows, highlighting the financial unsustainability of LFP recycling under conventional technological pathways.

These findings demonstrate that, under the current facility distribution, the economic viability of Europe’s battery recycling sector is heavily dependent on the market share of NCX chemistries. As LFP adoption increases—particularly in cost-sensitive EV markets—continuing with traditional recycling methods could lead to significant financial losses, posing a substantial risk to the economic sustainability of the industry. This analysis also highlights the need for technological adaptation, particularly through the potential deployment of direct recycling for LFP batteries. Without such innovations, the structural imbalance caused by the rising share of LFP chemistries could undermine profitability and jeopardize the economic sustainability of the European battery recycling sector.

Market Margin Shifts with Full Direct Recycling Adoption for LFP

Figure 22 Market margin shifts with direct recycling deployment

Continuing the methodology outlined in Section 2.3.5, Figure 22 illustrates annual profit projections across three chemistry scenarios—NCX-dominant, LFP-dominant, and Neutral—assuming full adoption of direct recycling for all LFP EoL batteries. Compared to the previous scenario (Figure 4.11), this technological shift notably reshapes the economic outlook.

In the LFP-dominant scenario, direct recycling transforms previously unprofitable outcomes—caused by reliance on conventional hydrometallurgical and pyro-hydro pathways—into sustained profitability by 2035. Across all scenarios, profits rise as direct recycling reduces processing costs and eliminates the need for energy-intensive cathode restructuring. Even in the neutral scenario, this technology significantly boosts financial returns, highlighting the scalability and economic advantages of applying direct recycling to LFP batteries.

These findings underscore the transformative impact of direct recycling in addressing LFP’s historical financial challenges. Without this technological advancement, the increasing market share of LFP chemistries would likely exacerbate financial losses, limiting the economic viability of expanding LFP recycling capacity.

Comparisons of Direct Recycling Adoption for LFP Batteries

Figure 23 Market margin comparison of different subsidy strategies on LFP recycling

Figure 23 builds on the previous analyses from Figures 21 and 22 by directly comparing two contrasting market scenarios: one where conventional hydrometallurgical and pyro-hydro

processes continue to dominate LFP recycling, and another where direct recycling is fully adopted for all LFP end-of-life (EoL) feedstock. In this comparison, the solid lines represent the expected annual market profitability under each scenario, while the dashed boundaries reflect the range of possible outcomes across different chemistry distributions—NCX-dominant, Neutral, and LFP-dominant scenarios.

The comparison highlights two critical insights. First, by 2035, the profitability gap between the two scenarios becomes substantial. In the neutral chemistry scenario, adopting direct recycling for LFP batteries leads to an additional \$260.1 million/year in profit compared to conventional recycling technologies. This indicates that fully integrating direct recycling into the LFP recycling framework could significantly boost overall market profitability, even under balanced chemistry market conditions. Second, without technological innovation, the increasing market share of LFP batteries presents a substantial financial risk. In a future where LFP chemistries dominate the EoL stock, relying solely on conventional recycling pathways could result in negative market profitability by 2035, posing a severe threat to the economic sustainability of Europe’s recycling sector.

This profitability gap underscores two potential strategies to ensure the financial viability of LFP recycling as its market share grows. The first is investment in or subsidies for new technology deployment, specifically targeting the adoption of direct recycling for LFP chemistries. By addressing technological barriers and enabling the necessary infrastructure adjustments, this strategy would allow recyclers to process LFP batteries more cost-effectively, reducing energy consumption and avoiding the economic losses associated with conventional methods.

Alternatively, policymakers could implement per-unit subsidies for each kilogram of LFP battery material recycled through conventional pathways. This measure would help offset the negative margins observed with traditional recycling technologies, providing short-term financial relief until more advanced technologies, like direct recycling, are widely adopted.

Given LFP’s increasing role in cost-sensitive electric vehicle markets and stationary energy storage applications, neglecting this profitability gap could hinder private sector investment in LFP

recycling infrastructure. The results suggest that embracing technological innovation through direct recycling offers a more sustainable long-term solution. It reduces the need for ongoing government subsidies, ensures economic viability, and supports the broader development of a circular battery economy in Europe.

3.2.3 Climate impact mitigation potential

Figure 24 GHG emission comparison of different subsidy strategies on LFP recycling

Figure 24 mirrors the analytical framework used in Figure 23 but focuses on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions rather than profitability. This comparison evaluates two distinct scenarios: one where LFP batteries continue to be recycled using conventional hydrometallurgical or pyro-hydro methods, and another where all LFP end-of-life (EoL) batteries are processed using direct recycling technology. The solid lines represent the projected annual GHG reductions under each scenario, while the dashed boundaries reflect variations based on different chemistry distributions—NCX-dominant, Neutral, and LFP-dominant market scenarios.

Overall, both scenarios demonstrate a significant decline in GHG emissions over time, highlighting the critical role of recycling in mitigating climate impacts within the EU's lithium-

ion battery (LIB) market. By 2035, the total potential GHG savings from LIB recycling could reach nearly 9 million tons of CO₂-equivalent per year—a substantial environmental benefit that underscores the importance of scaling recycling infrastructure as battery usage grows.

However, the additional benefit of introducing direct recycling for LFP batteries is not as significant as its economic impact. By 2035, the direct recycling scenario achieves an additional reduction of approximately 0.7 million tons of CO₂-equivalent per year compared to conventional recycling technologies. This smaller gap is primarily due to the inherently lower carbon footprint of LFP batteries relative to nickel- and cobalt-rich chemistries, as well as the comparatively lower energy demands of conventional LFP recycling processes.

Despite the narrower margin of environmental benefit, the adoption of direct recycling remains valuable from a climate mitigation perspective. As the share of LFP batteries in the EoL stock grows—particularly in cost-sensitive EV markets and stationary energy storage—maximizing recycling efficiency through advanced technologies will be essential for achieving long-term carbon neutrality goals.

In conclusion, while the economic benefits of direct recycling for LFP batteries are not significantly more pronounced than the GHG reductions, integrating this technology still offers meaningful environmental gains. Combining economic viability with climate mitigation strengthens the case for encouraging the deployment of direct recycling technologies in Europe's battery recycling sector, supporting both industrial sustainability and the EU's broader climate objectives.

4. Discussion

4.1 Technological lock-in and transition barriers

4.1.1 Path dependency in existing technologies

The technological trajectory of lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling is increasingly favoring mechanical pretreatment + hydrometallurgy, especially among newly planned facilities. However, legacy infrastructure and regional industrial structures create significant path dependencies, influencing the technological choices of both established recyclers in Europe and China's battery recycling industry.

Transition to Conventional Hydrometallurgy: A New Industry Standard

Despite the historical dominance of pyrometallurgical-based recycling, planned recycling facilities now overwhelmingly favor conventional hydrometallurgy. Industry data indicates that upcoming projects incorporate mechanical pretreatment and, in some cases, pyrolysis as an intermediate step to enhance metal recovery efficiency. Pyrolysis aids in removing volatile organic compounds and breaking down electrode binders, facilitating more efficient leaching processes. This hybrid approach—already widely implemented by Chinese recyclers—achieves high recovery rates while minimizing energy consumption and environmental impact. The shift signals a broader industry recognition that hydrometallurgy, combined with optimized pretreatment, is the most economically and environmentally viable solution.

While some established European recyclers continue to operate pyrometallurgical facilities, this persistence is largely a consequence of existing metallurgical infrastructure and business models. Many of these recyclers historically specialized in nickel and cobalt refining and adapted their smelting operations to accommodate spent LIBs. Since pyrometallurgy inherently produces high-purity Ni and Co metal, these companies could enter the battery recycling sector with minimal modification to their core operations. By retrofitting their smelting lines with hydrometallurgical extraction units, they were able to convert recovered metals into battery-grade salts (e.g., NiSO₄) while continuing to rely on their legacy processes. However, this approach struggles with lithium recovery, as lithium often remains in the slag phase rather than being effectively extracted for reuse.

This industrial inertia is particularly evident in firms that previously focused on NiMH battery recycling. When transitioning to lithium-based chemistries like NCM and LFP, many of these companies continued using pure pyrometallurgy, extracting Ni and Co for sale while discarding lithium in low-value slag materials. Now, with stricter lithium recovery regulations, these firms must retrofitting their facilities to comply with new requirements. However, this retroactive adaptation incurs high CapEx costs, making it financially burdensome for established pyrometallurgical recyclers to shift toward lithium-efficient processes.

China's Cross-Subsidization Model: A Different Path Dependency

While China leads in LIB recycling through its highly developed refining and hydrometallurgical industries, it also exhibits a form of path dependency—but one rooted in its economic structure rather than technical infrastructure. In China, large-scale recyclers effectively subsidize unprofitable LFP recycling through profits generated from NCX batteries. Given that NCX recycling yields high-value metals like nickel and cobalt, Chinese recyclers can afford to absorb losses from LFP recycling without seeking alternative technologies. This cross-subsidization model reduces economic pressure to innovate in LFP recycling, particularly for emerging methods like direct recycling.

Moreover, due to the lack of targeted government incentives for LFP direct recycling, Chinese recyclers have little motivation to develop or commercialize new technologies. Instead, only a handful of small ventures are actively exploring direct recycling approaches. This stands in stark contrast to the European market, where recyclers must navigate higher resource dependency and a less vertically integrated supply chain, making direct recycling a more strategically appealing solution.

Strategic Considerations for Europe: Direct Recycling as an Opportunity

For Europe, direct recycling presents both a technological and geopolitical opportunity. First, prioritizing direct recycling could reduce reliance on China's well-established hydrometallurgical and precursor material supply chains, creating a more independent and localized battery circular economy. Second, direct recycling produces cathode active material directly, bypassing China's

dominance in cathode precursor manufacturing. This aspect is particularly important given that Europe currently lags behind in battery material refining and precursor synthesis.

Recognizing these advantages, Europe's only pilot-scale LFP direct recycling facility is currently being developed in collaboration with Chinese researchers, suggesting early-stage interest in technology transfer and joint innovation. However, for direct recycling to become commercially viable, European policymakers and industry leaders must actively support R&D, incentivize deployment, and address existing technological gaps. Without targeted investment and regulatory support, the development of direct recycling may face the same stagnation seen in China, where path dependency inhibits innovation despite economic and environmental potential.

Thus, while the broader industry is moving toward hydrometallurgical dominance, regional differences in technological adaptation highlight the role of economic structures, industrial history, and policy frameworks in shaping the future of LIB recycling.

4.1.2 Economic challenges

Figure 25 Forecasted prices of key minerals, adopted from A. Yao et al [73]

As outlined in the results section, profitability in NCM recycling is largely driven by the high market value of nickel (Ni) and cobalt (Co), whereas LFP recycling remains economically challenging due to the low intrinsic value of its recovered materials. However, one limitation of this study is the assumption of fixed 2023 metal prices, which does not account for future fluctuations in commodity markets.

Figure 25 presents forecasted price trends for key battery materials. Both lithium and nickel prices are expected to decline, which could further compress recycling margins in the coming years. Since the economic viability of recycling is highly sensitive to material prices, as demonstrated in the sensitivity analysis, this trend raises concerns about whether current profit estimates will remain valid in the future.

Beyond material prices, capital expenditure (CapEx) remains a major constraint for recycling facilities. Previous studies (e.g., [51][55]) indicate that in the U.S., a facility capacity of approximately 50,000 t/year is required to achieve profitability, aligning with the scale estimated in this study. However, the equipment capital cost adjustment factor in this study was assumed to

be a uniform 90% of U.S. costs, based on industry interviews. In reality, adjustment factors vary by facility, and sourcing equipment from China could significantly lower costs. For instance, [XX] reports that smelter prices in China can be as low as 10–20% of those in Europe, meaning that strategic equipment sourcing could significantly improve margins by reducing CapEx burdens.

Additionally, as discussed in Section 4.1.1 on technological lock-in, Chinese recyclers are deeply invested in hydrometallurgical processes. With potential declines in lithium prices, some companies are considering modifying their recovery flows to extract iron phosphate (FePO_4) alongside lithium. However, current cost-benefit analyses indicate that FePO_4 recovery remains economically marginal, requiring further process optimization before widespread adoption.

Finally, an often-overlooked factor in battery recycling economics is the negative feedback loop between recycling and metal prices. As recycling capacity scales up, the increased supply of recovered cathode active materials (CAMs) could depress market prices, leading to a self-regulating effect that reduces recycling margins over time. This complex interaction between market dynamics and recycling economics warrants further research to better understand long-term price-recycling feedback mechanisms and their impact on industry sustainability.

4.1.3 Next-generation batteries

The emergence of next-generation battery technologies introduces new complexities to recycling, as evolving material compositions and degradation mechanisms may alter both economic incentives and technical feasibility. Among the most discussed advancements are solid-state batteries (SSBs), sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), and lithium-metal batteries (Li-S/Li-O₂). Each of these technologies presents unique challenges and opportunities for the recycling industry.

Solid-state batteries (SSBs) retain a cathode composition similar to conventional NCM batteries but replace the liquid electrolyte with a solid electrolyte, such as sulfide, oxide, or polymer-based materials. This shift affects recycling in two key ways. First, solid electrolytes increase production costs, making their recovery potentially valuable for improving recycling profitability. Unlike liquid electrolytes, which are currently not recovered, solid electrolytes may offer an additional revenue stream if extraction and reuse prove viable. Second, SSBs introduce new technical

challenges in cathode separation, as solid electrolytes complicate mechanical and chemical delamination processes. Additionally, solid electrolytes contribute to impurities in leaching operations, necessitating further refinement to maintain cathode metal purity.

Sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), while often compared to LFP batteries, introduce a different set of recycling challenges. SIBs are projected to be significantly cheaper than lithium-ion batteries—potentially 50–67% lower in cost—making them an attractive option for stationary storage and entry-level EVs. However, their use of sodium instead of lithium removes one of the primary economic drivers of LIB recycling. Since sodium has little market value, there is no clear economic incentive for dedicated SIB recycling, meaning that any recovery efforts would likely need to be policy-driven rather than market-driven. Moreover, the rise of SIBs could disrupt existing LIB recycling markets by reducing the volume of end-of-life (EoL) LFP batteries, thereby limiting economies of scale and increasing financial pressures on LFP recyclers. If SIBs replace a significant share of LFP applications, they could accelerate the transition away from LFP recycling altogether.

Lithium-metal batteries (Li-S / Li-O₂) represent another frontier in battery development, offering potentially higher energy densities but facing significant technical hurdles. Their primary degradation mechanisms—such as lithium dendrite formation and dead lithium accumulation—pose challenges for both safety and recyclability. Unlike LIBs, where established hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical methods exist, there is currently little research on the potential pathways for recycling lithium-metal chemistries. Given the early-stage nature of lithium-metal battery research, it is difficult to predict whether cost-effective recycling solutions will emerge in the near future.

Overall, next-generation batteries will reshape the recycling landscape, with SIBs introducing new material recovery challenges, SIBs reducing EoL LIB volumes, and lithium-metal batteries requiring further R&D. These shifts underscore the need for flexible recycling infrastructure and early-stage policy planning to ensure that future chemistries remain compatible with sustainable end-of-life management strategies.

4.2 Policy and industry strategies implications

4.2.1 Smart subsidy design

The economic challenges of LFP recycling necessitate smart subsidy mechanisms to ensure financial viability while advancing Europe’s resource security and circular economy goals. A market-driven cross-subsidization model, similar to China’s, could require NCX recyclers to offset LFP losses by meeting minimum resource recovery targets. However, this would place financial strain on emerging European recyclers who lack mature infrastructure and sufficient EoL stock. An alternative is direct per-kilogram subsidies for LFP recycling, estimated at \$1.5–\$2.0 per kg, which could gradually phase out as economies of scale improve. However, without higher lithium prices or technological advancements, long-term government support may be needed, increasing fiscal pressure. To balance this, an NCX collection fee from recyclers could help finance LFP recycling.

A more sustainable approach is to subsidize R&D and industrial deployment of direct recycling, enabling long-term cost reductions while fostering European leadership in battery circularity. Investing in early-stage technology development and infrastructure could improve industry-wide profitability, accelerate commercialization, and reduce reliance on imported cathode materials. Targeted subsidies for innovation rather than ongoing operational support would ensure economic and strategic resilience in Europe’s battery recycling sector.

4.2.2 Other policy design to facilitate new technology deployment

The development of standardized battery design and digital battery passports presents an opportunity to overcome critical barriers in direct recycling. Interviews with industry experts highlight three major challenges: (1) efficient separation of cathode active material (CAM), (2) precise battery state-of-health (SoH) assessment, and (3) quality control of recycled CAM.

First, automated disassembly remains impractical due to manufacturer-specific battery designs, requiring manual separation of CAM powder in pilot projects. Standardizing cell-level battery design—emphasizing durability, modularity, and recyclability—would enable mechanized sorting, drastically reducing labor costs and increasing process efficiency. EU regulations already

recommend design principles that enhance recyclability, which could accelerate direct recycling adoption.

Second, state-of-health and chemistry identification are crucial for maintaining material integrity. Direct recycling requires precise batch control, as batteries with 80% and 90% SoH cannot be mixed for relithiation, nor can NCM-811 and NCM-111 be processed together. Implementing digital battery passports would allow continuous tracking of battery usage history, chemistry, and degradation patterns, ensuring automated sorting and minimizing costly pre-processing assessments.

Finally, quality assurance for recycled CAM is necessary to ensure reliability in new batteries. While improved separation and classification would inherently enhance material consistency, digital battery passports could label batteries made from recycled CAM and enable post-market monitoring. This approach would facilitate early issue detection, streamline recalls, and provide valuable data for iterative improvements in recycling technologies.

By integrating standardization and traceability, Europe can accelerate the commercialization of direct recycling, reduce costs, and enhance overall material circularity, positioning itself at the forefront of sustainable battery innovation.

4.2.3 Supply chain strategy

Our analysis highlights the importance of a hybrid supply chain model that integrates decentralized pretreatment clusters with centralized recycling hubs to optimize logistics costs, capital investment, and material recovery efficiency. Decentralized pretreatment facilities (1–10k tons/year) can serve as localized shredding and sorting sites, reducing transportation costs by processing EoL batteries closer to collection points. This minimizes the need for hazardous battery transport, lowers regulatory and insurance costs, and allows for modular, low-risk investment, making it easier for new entrants to participate in the market.

At the same time, centralized recycling hubs (~100k tons/year) provide the economies of scale necessary for cost-effective hydrometallurgical and direct recycling. Large-scale processing

reduces per-unit costs and facilitates the co-location of refining and precursor material manufacturing, creating a more efficient circular material flow within regional industrial clusters. By consolidating high-value material processing within the EU, this approach also aligns with Europe's long-term strategy to enhance resource independence and reduce reliance on external supply chains.

By combining localized pretreatment clusters with regional mega-hubs, this supply chain model could reduce logistics costs while maintaining the material recovery efficiency. For policymakers and industry leaders, investing in modular pretreatment expansion alongside large-scale hub development presents a scalable, cost-effective, and resilient framework for the future of European battery recycling.

4.2.3 Joint venture strategies

An additional avenue for bolstering Europe's battery recycling involves joint ventures with leading Asian nations—such as China, Japan, and South Korea—who possess advanced refining expertise and well-established supply chains. By partnering with these industry pioneers, EU stakeholders can accelerate technology transfer, reduce capital expenses through co-investment, and broaden access to critical raw materials. Such collaborations could also foster standardized processes and quality benchmarks, ensuring compatibility across regions. Ultimately, a well-negotiated joint venture framework could synergize Europe's ambitious policy environment with Asia's industrial depth, delivering mutual benefits in sustainability, resource security, and economic growth.

4.3 Limitations and outlook

4.3.1 Methodological limitations

Most limitations of methodology were discussed in Section 2.4. For example, data access are limited. Further collaboration with industry stakeholders would improve real-world data accuracy. Also, the EverBatt model is an aggregation model; it treats each recycling route as a "black box", aggregating material flows and costs without detailed thermodynamic or kinetic modeling of individual process steps. While this enables multi-scenario comparisons, it overlooks fine-grained details with potential trade-offs and optimizations (e.g., alternative leaching pathways that reduce costs but increase emissions).

To address these limitations, developing a process-decomposed model integrated with chemical process simulation software (e.g., Aspen Plus) would enable more detailed thermodynamic and kinetic calculations at each stage. Additionally, incorporating uncertainty analysis (e.g., Monte Carlo simulations) would allow step-by-step breakdowns of cost, revenue, material recovery, and GHG emissions, providing uncertainty ranges by varying key process parameters—such as adjusting the leaching acid concentration by 1%. This approach would help identify technical, economic, and environmental bottlenecks, facilitating optimization-driven strategies to enhance process efficiency, profitability, and long-term sustainability.

4.3.2 Limitations in the background information

Many parameters in our model rely on assumptions due to data limitations and market uncertainties. One key factor is metal pricing, which, as discussed in Section 4.1.2, significantly impacts profitability and policy subsidy design. Additionally, price fluctuations introduce a negative feedback loop, where increased recycling supply can lower the market price of recovered materials, thereby reducing recycling margins. To better capture these dynamics, future research should incorporate scenario analysis for varying metal prices to assess their long-term influence on recycling economics.

Another limitation lies in capital cost adjustments, where a uniform adjustment factor (90% of the U.S. costs) was applied. In reality, different equipment types, suppliers, and regional factors lead to varying cost structures. Future work should refine these estimates by conducting more targeted interviews, expanding the scope beyond recyclers to include equipment manufacturers and chemical supply chain experts. This broader dataset would improve model accuracy and ensure that cost assumptions better reflect real-world industry conditions.

4.3.3 Limitations in research design

As outlined in the research design (Section 2.1), a comprehensive analysis of upstream (collection and sorting) and downstream (remanufacturing and reuse) processes was initially proposed. However, this study primarily focuses on recycling pathway comparison (step 1) and market

scenarios (step 3), excluding broader system-level effects. This omission creates certain comparability limitations, particularly for direct recycling.

For example, direct recycling does not account for sorting costs, which are essential for ensuring high-purity CAM recovery. In contrast, other recycling routes—such as hydrometallurgy and combined pyro-hydro processes—require fewer sorting steps but yield Ni and Co sulfates rather than fully reusable CAM. This imbalance means that direct recycling appears more economically favorable in the model, even though real-world implementation would require additional processing and quality control.

To address this limitation, future research should expand the system boundary to include upstream sorting costs and downstream material reuse factors, ensuring a more balanced comparison between recycling technologies. Integrating these additional steps would provide a clearer picture of the full economic and environmental trade-offs associated with each pathway.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling pathways within the evolving European regulatory landscape, integrating both micro-level techno-economic analysis and macro-scale market projections. By evaluating hydrometallurgical, pyro-hydrometallurgical, and direct recycling methods, we elucidate critical trade-offs in economic viability, material recovery, and greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation potential. Our findings underscore that while hydrometallurgical processes remain the industry standard for nickel- and cobalt-rich cathodes, direct recycling holds significant promise for lithium iron phosphate (LFP) chemistries, offering a potential pathway toward sustainable and cost-effective LIB circularity.

At the market scale, scenario-based projections reveal a structural imbalance in the economic feasibility of LIB recycling, particularly as LFP adoption accelerates. Current recycling infrastructures, optimized for high-value chemistries, may face economic stagnation or contraction without targeted policy interventions. Our analysis suggests that direct recycling, coupled with design standardization and digital tracking systems such as “battery passports,” could enhance the economic and environmental performance of LIB recycling. These measures would not only streamline material recovery but also facilitate compliance with stringent EU recovery mandates. Despite these insights, challenges remain. The scalability of direct recycling requires further technological refinement and industry adoption, particularly in ensuring high-purity cathode active material (CAM) recovery. Moreover, uncertainties in global commodity prices introduce volatility into long-term profitability forecasts. To address these limitations, future research should expand model fidelity by incorporating real-world process validation and refining cost estimations through industry collaboration. Additionally, exploring synergies between battery second-life applications and recycling infrastructures could further optimize material circularity.

Ultimately, our findings provide an evidence-based framework for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers to align LIB recycling strategies with Europe’s broader sustainability goals. By fostering innovation in recycling technologies, designing targeted financial incentives, and integrating robust regulatory frameworks, the transition toward a resilient, closed-loop battery economy can be accelerated. This study underscores the necessity of a coordinated, multi-faceted

approach to ensure that LIB recycling not only meets economic viability thresholds but also serves as a cornerstone of Europe's long-term decarbonization strategy.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Process Flowsheets

Figure A.1 Flowsheets for basic recycling processes

Figure A.2 Flowsheets for combined process 1

Figure A.3 Flowsheets for combined process 2

Figure A.4 Flowsheets for direct recycling, adopted from EverBatt [57]

Appendix B. Modelling Parameters

Table B.1 Metal Price

\$/kg	Selected
Co	\$ 27.20
Ni	\$ 17.20
Mn	\$ 1.00

Table B.2 Reagent Price

\$/kg	Selected
Ammonia	\$ 0.53
Ammonium Bicarbonate	\$ 0.53
Ammonium Hydroxide	\$ 0.53
Carbon Dioxide	\$ 0.27
Citric Acid	\$ 1.95
Coke	\$ 0.31
Hydrochloric Acid	\$ 0.57
Hydrogen Peroxide	\$ 1.46
Lime	\$ 0.13
Limestone	\$ 0.13
Lithium Carbonate	\$ 17.14
Lithium Hydroxide	\$ 34.89
Nitrogen	\$ 0.30
NMP	\$ 2.70
Oxygen	\$ 0.20
Phosphoric Acid	\$ 1.14
Sand	\$ 0.05
Slag (copper)	\$ 0.02
Slag (lead)	\$ 0.02
Soda Ash	\$ 0.14
Sodium Hydroxide	\$ 0.45
Sulfuric Acid	\$ 0.08

Table B.3 Regional Specific Parameters

	Selected	U.S.	Europe	China	Korea
Equipment cost adjustment (%)	90%	100%	90%	61%	80%
Direct labor (\$/hr)	\$ 32.00	\$ 38.12	\$ 32.00	\$ 3.00	\$ 10.00
Electricity cost (\$/kWh)	\$ 0.17	\$ 0.085	\$ 0.17	\$ 0.088	\$ 0.076
Natural gas cost (\$/MMBTU)	\$ 13.55	\$ 7.77	\$ 13.55	\$ 12.00	\$ 12.00
Water cost (\$/gal)	\$ 0.009	\$ 0.005	\$ 0.009	\$ 0.002	\$ 0.003
Wastewater discharge cost (\$/gal)	\$ 0.013	\$ 0.006	\$ 0.013	\$ 0.003	\$ 0.003
Landfill cost (tip fee \$/ton)	\$ 63.500	\$ 54.03	\$ 63.50	\$ 10.00	\$ 20.00

Table B.4 Example of GREET materials data (partial)

	Limestone	Hydrochloric Acid	Citric Acid	Soda Ash	Lithium Carbonate
Energy Use: mmBtu					
Total Energy	0.108	27.651	9.950	5.082	115.604
Fossil fuels	0.107	24.964	13.548	5.075	112.816
Coal	0.005	5.127	2.988	4.241	80.944
Natural gas	0.011	18.946	9.652	0.079	5.763
Petroleum	0.092	0.891	0.909	0.755	26.109
Water consumption (gal)	27	1,245	6,520	31	11,867
Total Emissions: grams					
VOC	3.013	265.320	1,044.114	80.581	1,847.870
CO	18.143	1,050.649	849.584	497.677	8,131.533
NOx	15.094	1,611.899	1,843.212	289.167	16,108.437
PM10	3.089	152.182	296.567	152.467	2,949.478
PM2.5	0.545	99.010	110.760	96.830	2,082.195
SOx	1.707	850.806	952.250	164.204	13,846.535
BC	0.110	9.501	12.375	4.313	192.302
OC	0.096	29.449	20.011	7.740	359.942
CH4	10.490	4,532.141	2,788.450	696.460	15,331.821
N2O	0.063	39.664	576.214	1.001	77.667
CO2	8,378	1,710,066	1,100,350	618,052	10,745,213
CO2 (VOC, CO, CO2)	8,416	1,712,544	1,104,939	619,086	10,763,751
GHGs	8,745	1,858,430	1,345,342	640,113	11,241,842
Urban Emissions: grams					
VOC	0.274	16.051	229.094	1.810	73.733
CO	0.172	109.126	35.087	1.407	143.057
NOx	0.268	201.403	52.103	3.249	321.872
PM10	0.046	19.734	1.847	0.368	36.596
PM2.5	0.039	16.547	1.490	0.321	29.883
SOx	0.105	169.909	10.509	0.959	306.435
BC	0.005	0.812	0.153	0.035	2.245
OC	0.007	4.045	0.469	0.069	4.524

Table B.5 Example of GREET energy data (partial)

	Stationary Use			
	Total		Urban	
	Feedstock	Fuel	Feedstock	Fuel
Total energy	101,848	1,970,554		
Fossil fuels	99,995	1,544,058		
Coal	3,606	725,210		
Natural gas	83,593	809,838		
Petroleum	12,796	9,009		
Water consumption	9	164		
VOC	13.156	1.978	0.363	0.652
CO	23.268	30.931	1.463	10.663
NOx	29.715	68.473	1.959	23.772
PM10	6.559	8.241	0.030	2.872
PM2.5	1.211	6.907	0.026	2.379
SOx	14.117	72.562	0.220	26.566
BC	0.096	0.330	0.003	0.108
OC	0.195	1.877	0.009	0.595
CH4	258.020	12.951		
N2O	0.677	1.921		
CO2	6,345	121,456		
CO2 (w/ C in VOC & CO)	6,423	121,510		
GHGs	14,297	122,421		

Table B.6 Energy mix in different regions

Name			Default Locations			
			U.S.	Europe	China	Korea
Electricity generation data	Generation mix	Residual oil				
		NG				
		Coal				
		Biomass				
		Nuclear				
		Hydro				
	Others					
	T&D Loss					
Environmental impacts of electricity at wall outlet (per mmBtu electricity)						
Total energy (btu)			2,072,402	1,804,921	2,436,098	2,265,920
Fossil fuels			1,644,053	1,227,818	1,985,208	1,848,748
Coal			728,816	122,875	1,865,532	1,162,665
Natural gas			893,431	1,100,604	88,446	629,130
Petroleum			21,805	4,339	31,230	56,952
Water consumption (gal)			173	190	337	124
VOC (g)			15.134	11.754	17.286	16.939
CO			54.199	43.845	69.119	65.765
NOx			98.189	58.810	151.724	132.843
PM10			14.800	5.565	30.981	21.968
PM2.5			8.119	4.346	14.103	11.303
SOx			86.679	26.921	194.891	136.196
BC			0.426	0.299	0.636	0.604
OC			2.072	2.126	1.335	2.026
CH4			270.971	206.705	319.766	299.966
N2O			2.597	1.497	4.794	3.634
CO2			127,801	79,114	194,178	158,314
CO2 (w/ C in VOC & CO)			127,933	79,220	194,340	158,470
GHGs			136,717	85,788	205,178	168,401

Appendix C. Interview question list

I. Policy & Regulatory Considerations

1. Feasibility of EU Battery Regulation Targets

- How realistic and achievable are the targets set by the 2023 EU Battery Regulation (e.g., recovery rates, recycled content mandates)?
- What are the potential barriers to compliance, and how might regional differences in infrastructure or policy implementation affect outcomes?

2. Generalized Recycling Processes

- Are there other generalized recycling processes (beyond hydrometallurgy, pyrometallurgy, and direct recycling) that should be explored to align with EU regulatory goals?

II. Specific Recycling Technology (here use DR as an example)

3. Challenges & Opportunities

- What are the key technical, economic, and scalability challenges of direct recycling?
- How does direct recycling's CAPEX/OPEX profile compare to hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy?
- How do regional differences (e.g., labor costs, energy prices) influence CAPEX/OPEX for direct recycling?

4. Technical Processes

- After obtaining degraded cathode powder, how is re-lithiation performed to restore electrochemical performance?
- What technical challenges arise when scaling up direct recycling for LFP batteries (e.g., contamination control, consistency)?
- Can direct recycling methods developed for LFP cathodes be adapted for NMC chemistries? What modifications are required?

5. Material Quality & Competitiveness

- How do recycled materials from direct recycling compare to primary materials in terms of performance and cost?
- What strategies ensure recycled materials meet industry standards for reuse in new batteries?

III. Economic & Market Dynamics

6. Regional Variations

- Are there regional differences in the economic viability of recycling technologies (e.g., due to subsidies, energy costs, or labor)?

7. Market Acceptance

- What policies or incentives could accelerate market acceptance of recycled materials (e.g., carbon credits, procurement mandates)?
-

V. Environmental & Climate Impact

9. GHG Mitigation

- How does direct recycling's carbon footprint compare to other technologies, especially under varying regional energy mixes?
-

VI. Future Prospects & Innovation

10. Recycling's Role in Circular Economy

- What are the long-term prospects for direct recycling, particularly with evolving cathode chemistries (e.g., high-nickel, solid-state)?
- How might breakthroughs in material recovery (e.g., binder removal, lithium replenishment) address current limitations?

11. Cross-Technology Synergies

- Could hybrid approaches (e.g., combining direct recycling with hydrometallurgy for specific components) improve viability?

Appendix D. List of computation equations

$$\text{Recycling Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{kg feedstock}} \right] = \frac{\text{Total Direct Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] + \text{Total Indirect Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right]}{\text{Facility Capacity} \left[\frac{\text{kg feedstock}}{\text{year}} \right]}$$

$$\text{Total Direct Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] = \text{CapEx} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] + \text{Reagent Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] + \text{Labor Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] + \text{Utility Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right]$$

$$\text{CapEx} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] = \text{Fixed Capital Investment} [\$] \times \frac{\text{Interest Rate} \times (1 + \text{Interest Rate})^{\text{Lifetime}}}{(1 + \text{Interest Rate})^{\text{Lifetime} - 1}} \left[\frac{\%}{\text{year}} \right] \times \frac{1}{100} \left[\frac{1}{\%} \right]$$

$$\text{Fixed Capital Investment} [\$] = \text{Capital Investment Factor} \times \sum_i \text{Equipment}_i \times \text{Price}_{\text{Equip}_i} [\$]$$

$$\text{Reagent Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] = \sum_i \text{Reagent}_i \left[\frac{\text{kg reagent}}{\text{year}} \right] \times \text{Price}_{\text{Reagent}_i} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{kg reagent}} \right]$$

$$\text{Labor Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] = \sum_i \text{Number of Labors}_i \times \text{Working Hours}_i \left[\frac{\text{hour}}{\text{year}} \right] \times \text{Wage}_i \left[\frac{\$}{\text{hour}} \right]$$

$$\text{Utility Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] = \sum_i \text{Utility}_i \left[\frac{\text{unit utility}}{\text{year}} \right] \times \text{Cost}_i \left[\frac{\$}{\text{unit utility}} \right]$$

$$\text{Total Indirect Cost} \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right] = \sum_i \text{Indirect Cost Factor}_i \times \text{Direct Cost Item}_i \left[\frac{\$}{\text{year}} \right]$$

$$\text{Price}_{\text{equip}_i}(R) = \left[\text{Price}_{\text{equip}_i}(R_0) \times \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^p + k \right] \times \text{Adjustment Factor}_i$$

$$\text{Revenue} = \sum_i \text{Product}_i \times \text{Unit Price}_i$$

$$\text{Margin} = \text{Revenue} - \text{Recycling Cost}$$

$$\text{GHG}_{\text{recycling}}^{\text{total}} = (\sum_i \text{Material}_i \times \text{EF}_i)_{\text{materials}} + (\sum_j \text{Energy}_j \times \text{EF}_j)_{\text{energy}} + (\sum_k \Delta \text{CO}_{2,k})_{\text{process}}$$

$$\text{GHG}_{\text{virgin}}^{\text{total}} = \sum_i (\text{mass}_i^{\text{rec}} \times \text{EF}_i^{\text{virgin}})$$

$$\text{Net GHG}_{\text{saving}} = \text{GHG}_{\text{recycling}}^{\text{total}} - \text{GHG}_{\text{virgin}}^{\text{total}}$$

Appendix E. Table of equipment parameters

Table E.1 Equipment cost list

Equipment	Capa. Adj.	Cost = (a*x ^b +c)*adj. (2019\$)			adj.
		a	b	c	
Air classifier	0.3	51600	1	0	1.416421
Ball mill	0.4	65240.12	0.69	0	2.029851
Brine soak	1	31862	0	0	2.029851
Briquetter	1	16048	0	0	2.06269
Calciner	0.4	1313832	0.512	0	1.416421
Centrifuge	1	186335	0	0	2.029851
Conveyor	1	20500	0	0	1.416421
Crusher	1	7242.4	0.5497	0	2.06269
Cyclone	1	64895.06	0.96	0	2.029851
Dryer	0.4	591236.1	0.6	0	2.029851
Eddy current separator	0.5	160000	0	0	2.06949
Electrowinning cell	1	684243	0.507	0	1.416421
Evaporator	1	500000	0	0	1.416421
Filter press	0.5	173000	0	0	1.416421
Froth flotation cell	1	3819.05	1.0285	0	1.34321
Furnace+saggar handling system	1	3800000	0	0	1
Gas treatment	1	1000000	0	0	1
Granulator	1	29902	0.6671	0	1.416421
Heat treatment furnace	1	507038	0.64	0	1.416421
Hopper	1	38700	0	0	1.416421
Hydrocyclone	1	50300	0	0	1.416421
Leaching tank	0.3	473892	0.4481	0	1.416421
Mixing tank	0.3	473892	0.4481	0	1.416421
Oxidizer	0.4	494284	0.7601	0	1.416421
Precipitation tank	1	473892	0.4481	0	1.416421
Pump	1	3009	0	0	2.06269
Screen, DSM	1	11000	1	0	1.416421
Screen, vibrating	1	18800	1	0	1.416421
Skid steer	1	40000	0	0	1
Smelter	1	6137979	0.48	0	1.416421
Solvent extraction unit	1	473892	0.4481	0	1.416421
Supercritical CO2 system	1	6088158	0.6909	0	1.563518
Water treatment	1	1000000	0	0	1
Wet granulator	1	29902	0.6671	0	1.416421
Wheel loader	1	150000	0	0	1

Table E.2 Equipment power usage list

Equipment	Power rating = $m \cdot x^n + p$ (KW)			person-hr/day
	m	n	p	
Air classifier	74.57	0	0	6
Ball mill	33.98638	1.0061	0	6
Brine soak	7.457	0	0	6
Briquetter	74.57	0	0	6
Calciner	5861.111	0	0	12
Centrifuge	0	0	0	
Conveyor	14.914	0	0	2
Crusher	74.57	0	0	6
Cyclone	74.57	0	0	6
Dryer	728.7428	1	0	6
Eddy current separator	0	0	0	
Electrowinning cell	0	0	0	
Evaporator	0	0	0	6
Filter press	14.914	0	0	6
Froth flotation cell	0.4513	0.6913	0	6
Furnace+saggar handling system	0	0	0	24
Gas treatment	1000	0	0	12
Granulator	1.3607	1	-0.5806	6
Heat treatment furnace	5861.111	0	0	12
Hopper	14.914	0	0	6
Hydrocyclone	74.57	0	0	6
Leaching tank	14.914	1	0	12
Mixing tank	14.914	1	0	6
Oxidizer	5861.111	0	0	12
Precipitation tank	14.914	1	0	12
Pump	3.191596	1	0	4
Screen, DSM	14.914	1	0	6
Screen, vibrating	14.914	1	0	6
Skid steer	0	0	0	4
Smelter	0	0	0	24
Solvent extraction unit	14.914	1	0	12
Supercritical CO2 system	1000	0	0	12
Water treatment	1000	0	0	12
Wet granulator	1.3607	1	-0.5806	6
Wheel loader	0	0	0	20

Appendix F. Table of cost items

Cost Items	Computed/Estimated as
I. Direct Investment	I.A + I.B+I+C3:C32.C+I.D
A. Equipment	I.A.1+I.A.2+I.A.3+I.A.4+I.A.5
1. Purchased equipment	Sum of (equipment * unit cost)
2. Installation	40% of I.A.1
3. Instrumentation and Control	20% of I.A.1
4. Piping, installed	20% of I.A.1
5. Electrical, installed	10% of I.A.1
B. Buildings, process and auxiliary	25% of I.A.1
C. Service facilities and yard improvements	60% of I.A.1
D. Land	8% of I.A.1
II. Indirect Investment	II.A+II.B+II.C
A. Engineering and supervision	10% of I
B. Construction expense and contractor's fee	10% of I
C. Contingency	5% of I
III. Fixed Capital Investment	I + II
IV. Working Capital	10% of III
V. Total Capital Investment	III + IV
VI. Manufacturing Costs	VI.A+VI.B+VI.C
A. Direct product costs	Sum of (VI.A.1~7)
1. Raw material / reagent	Sum of (reagent * unit cost)
2. Operating Labor	Sum of (labor * hours * salary)
3. Direct supervisory and clerical labor	15% of VI.A.2
4. Utility (energy / water)	Sum of (utility * unit cost)
5. Maintenance and repairs	5% of III
6. Operating supplies	15% of VI.A.5
7. Laboratory charges	10% of VI.A.2
8. Patents and royalties	1% of VIII
B. Fixed charges	VI.B.1+VI.B.2+VI.B.3+VI.B.4+VI.B.5
1. Depreciation	(III-I.D)/plant lifetime
2. Tax	Depends on profit, assume 10% of IV
3. Insurance	1% of III
4. Rent	5% of (I.B + I.D)
5. Financing (interest)	5% of V
C. Plant overhead costs	20% of VI.A
VII. General Expense	VII.A+VII.B+VII.C
A. Administrative expense	15% of VI.A.2
B. Distribution and selling costs	6% of VI
C. R&D costs	5% of VI
VIII. Total Product Cost	VI + VII

Appendix G. Assumption list of scenario estimates

Key structural assumptions in Xu's model include:

- EV lifespan follows Weibull distribution (1-20 years, mode=15)
- Battery replacement rates decrease from 50% pre-2020 to 0% post-2020 as durability improves
- LFP batteries assume 20-year lifespan vs. 15 years for NCX types
- Second-life applications delay recycling by 10 years for 75% of batteries

EU estimation:

- 2024 EU EV stock contribution (27.65% global share)[65]
- 2024 EU sales contribution (23.13% global share)[66,70]
- Arithmetic mean of these metrics (25.39%) maintained through 2035

Implies:

- No relative acceleration/decline in EU EV adoption vs. global trends
- Homogeneous battery chemistry preferences across regions
- Comparable vehicle retirement patterns between EU and global fleets

Battery chemistry assumptions:

1. **NCX Scenario:** Nickel-cobalt (NCX) variants dominate with:
 - Annual cathode chemistry shifts (NCA→NCM111→523→622→811→955)
 - Cobalt content reduction from 20% (NCM111) to 5% (NCM955)
 - Specific energy improvements from 160 Wh/kg to 202 Wh/kg
2. **LFP Scenario:** Lithium iron phosphate reaches 60% market share by 2030 with:
 - 129 Wh/kg specific energy (vs. NCX's 202 Wh/kg)
 - 2× higher cycle life than NCX batteries
 - Complete cobalt elimination in LFP portion
3. **Neutral Scenario:** Arithmetic mean of NCX/LFP shares at annual resolution

Other technical parameters:

- BatPaC v3.1 model simulations for 48 battery configurations

- Cell-to-pack mass ratios of 65-72% depending on chemistry
- Silicon-enhanced anodes (5-10% Si) in advanced NCM variants
- 8-year minimum lifespan with Weibull-distributed retirement ($\alpha=2.5$, $\beta=15$)
- 10-year second-life buffer for 75% of automotive batteries
- Recycling delay factors of 1.35-1.85 \times initial lifespan depending on chemistry

Appendix H. Table of recovery rate

Table H.1 Recovery rate of conventional hydrometallurgy

Conventional Hydro	Recycling efficiencies			Source	Annotation
	Upstream	Process	Total		
Disassembly Total		99%	99%	Assumption	
Mechanical Pretreatment					
Shredding	99%	100%	99%	Assumption	
Electrolyte recovery	99%	80%	79%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.173	Evaporation + condensation
Magnetic separation	99%	98%	97%	Assumption	
Zigzag 1, Aluminum		95%	95%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Zigzag 1, Plastic		90%	90%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	Including electronic components
Filter		85%	85%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	Sieving efficiency (for hydrometallurgy)
Air classifier, Copper foil		98%	98%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Air classifier, Aluminum foil		97%	97%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Air classifier, Plastic film		95%	95%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Hydrometallurgy					
Leaching	97%	98%	95%	Jung, J. (2023) p. 15-p. 28	H2SO4 + H2O2
Filter / washing		98%	98%	Jung, J. (2023) p. 15-p. 28	Graphite
Cementation / filtering		97%	97%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Cu
Precipitation / Filtering Fe		92%	92%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Fe
Precipitation / Filtering Al		92%	92%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Al
Co + Ni extraction	95%	99%	94%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	
Extraction Co	94%	99%	93%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	
Crystallization Co	93%	99%	92%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Co
Critallization Ni	94%	99%	93%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Ni
Extraction Mn	95%	99%	94%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	
Crystallization Mn	94%	99%	93%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Mn
Precipitation / Filtering Li	95%	80%	76%	Ali et al (2024), Blomeke et al (2022)	Li

Table H.2 Recovery rate of conventional hydrometallurgy

Combined Process 1	Recycling efficiencies		Source	Annotation
	Upstream	Process		
Dissassembly Total		99%	99.00%	Assumption
Pyrometallurgy alloy:				
Cobalt		96%	96.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Nickel		98%	98.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Copper		95%	95.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Iron alloy+slag (A+S)		99%	99.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Pyrometallurgy slag:				
Manganese		95%	95.00%	Assumption
Lithium		90%	90.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Aluminium		97%	97.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Iron (A+S)		99%	99.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Limestone CaO		98%	98.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Quartz sand / silicon (SiO2)		99%	99.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2
Hydrometallurgy alloy:				
Cementation / filtering	95%	95%	90.25%	Assumption
Precipitation / Filtering Fe	99%	90%	89.10%	Assumption
Co + Ni extraction	96%	99%	95.04%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46
Extraction co	95%	99%	94.09%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46
Crystallization Co	94%	99%	93.15%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46
Crystallization Ni	95%	99%	94.09%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46
Hydrometallurgy slag:				
Filter	98%	90%	88.20%	Assumption
Filter	99%	98%	97.02%	Assumption
Precipitation / Filtering Fe	99%	90%	89.10%	Assumption
Precipitation / Filtering Al	97%	90%	87.30%	Assumption
Extraction Mn	95%	99%	94.05%	Expert estimate
Crystallization Mn	94%	99%	93.11%	Expert estimate
Precipitation / filtering Li	90%	85%	76.50%	Umicore Patent WO 2020/104164 A1

Table H.3 Recovery rate of combined process 2

Combined Process 2	Recycling efficiencies			Source	Annotation
	upstream	Process	Total		
Disassembly Total		99%	99.00%	Assumption	
Magnetic separation		98%	98.00%	Assumption	
Filter general		85%	85.00%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	Sieving efficiency (for hydrometallurgy)
Filter Cobalt		96%	98.00%	Accurec BATTERY RECYCLING DATASHEET	
Filter Nickel		97%	97.00%	Accurec BATTERY RECYCLING DATASHEET	
Filter Graphite		79%	79.00%	Accurec BATTERY RECYCLING DATASHEET	
Zigzag, Copper foil		98%	98.00%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Zigzag, Aluminum foil		97%	97.00%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Zigzag, Plastic film		95%	95.00%	LithoRec_II_Final_Report(2016) p.46	
Pyrometallurgy alloy:					
Cobalt	98%	98%	96.04%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2; Accurce battery recycli	Selectivity alloy / slag
Nickel	97%	98%	95.06%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2; Accurce battery recycli	Selectivity alloy / slag
Copper	94%	98%	92.12%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2; Accurce battery recycli	Selectivity alloy / slag
Iron (A+S)	86%	99%	85.14%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2; Accurce battery recycli	Recoverable in alloy and slag
Pyrometallurgy slag:					
Manganese	85%	95%	80.75%	Assumption	Selectivity alloy / slag
Lithium	85%	90%	76.50%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2	Rest in fly ash (loss)
Aluminium	85%	97%	82.45%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2	Selectivity alloy / slag
Iron (A+S)	86%	99%	85.14%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2; Accurce battery recycli	Recoverable in alloy and slag
Limestone CaO		98%	98.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2	Slag generator
Quartz sand SiO2		99%	99.00%	Umicore Patent US 8,840,702 B2	Slag generator
Hydrometallurgy alloy:					
Cementation / filtering	92%	99%	91.20%	Assumption	Cu
Precipitation / Filtering Fe	85%	90%	76.63%	Assumption	Fe
Co + Ni extraction	96%	99%	95.08%	Expert estimate	
Extraction co	95%	99%	94.13%	Expert estimate	
Crystallization Co	94%	99%	93.19%	Expert estimate	Co
Critallization Ni	95%	99%	94.13%	Expert estimate	Ni
Hydrometallurgy slag:					
Filter	98%	90%	88.20%	Assumption	CaSO4
Filter	99%	98%	97.02%	Assumption	SiO2
Precipitation / Filtering Fe	85%	90%	76.63%	Assumption	Fe
Precipitation / Filtering Al	82%	90%	74.21%	Assumption	Al
Extraction Mn	81%	99%	79.94%	Expert estimate	
Crystallization Mn	80%	99%	79.14%	Expert estimate	Mn
Precipitation / filtering Li	77%	85%	65.03%	Expert estimate	Li